

OVERALL RISK ANALYSIS - L'AQUILA, ITALY

REPORT

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Index

Introduction.....	4
1. Research objectives and methodology	6
1.1 General and specific objectives	6
1.2 Methodological approach	6
1.3 Data sources and analytical tools	8
2. Data collection and Overall Risk Analysis of the urban context.....	10
2.1 Territorial and Historical Framework	10
Geographical and morphological setting.....	10
Historical and urban development of the city of L’Aquila	10
Administrative structure and current planning framework	12
2.2 Analysis of the urban and socio-demographic system	14
Structure of urban fabrics.....	14
Population density and distribution	14
Socioeconomic structure and social vulnerability	15
Condition of the building stock and post-earthquake reconstruction processes.....	16
2.3 Analysis of infrastructure and services	18
Mobility and transport networks	18
Distribution of essential services (healthcare, education, emergency response)	19
Complementary services	20
Cultural resilience and territorial attractiveness.....	20
2.4 Analysis of the biophysical and environmental system	23
Morphology and geology.....	23
3. Analysis of natural and climate-related risks	36
3.1 Hydrogeological risk	36
Hydrographic system and flood-prone areas.....	36
3.2 Landslide risk	40
Geomorphological dynamics and slope instability	40
3.3 Seismic risk	44
Historical seismicity and building vulnerability.....	44
3.4 Climate and environmental risks	47

Land Surface Temperature (LST)	47
Thermal anomalies and Urban Heat Island (UHI)	48
Irradiance	54
Sky View Factor (SVF), Incident radiation and Simplified UTCI.....	56
3.5 Future climate scenarios	61
Local meteorological data	61
Analysis of future climate scenarios	67
Risk indices (1923-2023)	74
4. Analysis and study of critical areas	78
4.1 Identification of critical areas.....	78
Selection criteria.....	78
Aree oggetto di analisi	78
Tools and operational phases.....	79
4.2 Climate Walk.....	81
Survey methodology	81
In situ survey results	82
Interpretive summary	86
4.3 Focus Area – Francesco Rossi barracks	87
Model setup and methodology	87
Construction and environmental parametersi	87
ENVI-met simulation results.....	87
Analysis of the ENVI-met simulated points.....	103
5. Conclusions and operational recommendations	108
Summary of the main findings	108
Recommendations for planning and risk governance.....	109
Proposals for future developments.....	111

Introduction

The activity carried out for the *Overall Risk Analysis* (ORA) report concerned the case study of the city of L’Aquila, with a specific focus on the area of the Francesco Rossi Barracks, located in the immediate vicinity of the historic city centre. This analysis constitutes a significant component of the research and innovation activities developed within the *PNRR Project CHANGES – Cultural Heritage Active Innovation for Next-Gen Sustainable Society*, specifically under *Spoke 7*.

Beyond defining both the general and specific territorial and environmental conditions of the study area, the report proposes an advanced methodological framework to support urban planning and territorial management, developing an integrated model for the assessment and monitoring of risks deriving from the natural and anthropogenic characteristics of the context.

The adopted approach is fully aligned with national and European objectives concerning climate change adaptation and the mitigation of urban vulnerabilities, to be pursued also through regeneration interventions in historic cities and areas particularly exposed to environmental risks.

L’Aquila serves as a particularly relevant case study: a monumental centre of high historical and architectural value, engaged for over fifteen years in a post-earthquake reconstruction process that has profoundly transformed its physical and socio-economic fabric. This condition has highlighted the need for analytical tools able to connect territorial dynamics with environmental and social transformations occurring over medium- and long-term temporal scales.

The methodology developed integrates multi-scale territorial data, geographic information systems (GIS), CORINE Land Cover analysis, land-use mapping, remotely sensed indices (e.g., LST), and digital terrain models (DTM/DSM). This framework enables an in-depth reading of the relationships between morphology, surface cover, soil permeability, and phenomena of thermal accumulation.

CORINE analyses describe the structure of the urban and peri-urban territory across its different components - artificial, agricultural, forested, and natural surfaces - capturing the evolution of transformations that have occurred over recent decades. The integration with terrain models has allowed the interpretation of interactions among orography, natural ventilation, and the spatial concentration of thermal anomalies.

The resulting heat maps highlight the spatial distribution of surface-temperature anomalies and perceived climatic comfort, rapidly identifying the most vulnerable areas and potential mitigation strategies. The combined use of CORINE maps and thermal models demonstrates how the increase in impermeable surfaces and the reduction of continuous

vegetation weaken the capacity of the urban system to regulate energy and water flows, amplifying exposure to urban heat-island phenomena.

At the same time, the analysis quantifies the role of remaining green areas - urban parks, gardens, and forest belts - which act as ecological infrastructures capable of reducing temperatures, mitigating pollution, and strengthening environmental resilience.

The methodology integrates physical-environmental indicators (temperature, humidity, albedo, permeability), morphological indicators (slope, aspect, roughness), and vegetation indicators derived from multispectral data. These variables, modelled within the GIS environment, build an interactive and replicable knowledge base useful for forecasting scenario simulations and the evaluation of mitigation strategies.

The analysis also provides quantitative parameters for identifying new green areas, designing climate-resilient public spaces, and defining low-impact architectural and infrastructural solutions.

The aim of the report is not merely descriptive: the construction of an advanced territorial knowledge system is intended to support transparent, evidence-based decision-making processes in urban and environmental planning.

Within the specificity of the case study (cf. 4.3), the ORA enables the identification of operational targets for sustainable regeneration and climate-risk adaptation, linking land cover, microclimatic quality, and green infrastructure with projected climate-change trends. The future scenarios modelled (2030, 2050, 2100) are particularly relevant when applied to the area of Francesco Rossi barracks, a large building complex of uncertain current use and a strategic node in ongoing urban-regeneration processes.

The maps and models produced can be used to define intervention priorities, compare alternative mitigation strategies, optimize resources, and enhance the overall resilience of the urban system.

Ultimately, the *Overall Risk Analysis* for L’Aquila proposes a rigorous, multidisciplinary approach based on the integration of environmental analyses, geospatial data, climatic modelling, and territorial assessments. The result is a solid, multisectoral, forward-looking knowledge framework capable of representing interactions among natural and anthropogenic risks and guiding sustainable regeneration strategies for the city and, in particular, for the Francesco Rossi barracks.

1. Research objectives and methodology

1.1 General and specific objectives

The general objective of this study is to construct an integrated knowledge framework assessing the overall risk level of the urban context of the city of L’Aquila, with the aim of supporting territorial planning, urban regeneration, and climate adaptation strategies. The analysis seeks to evaluate the physical, environmental, and socio-economic vulnerability of the urban system of L’Aquila through a multidimensional approach that considers the interactions among natural, infrastructural, and demographic factors within a broader perspective of territorial resilience.

The specific objectives of the study are to:

- reconstruct the territorial, urban, and environmental context of the study area, outlining its main morphological and functional components.
- identify and map the principal natural and anthropogenic risk factors (hydrogeological, seismic, climatic-environmental).
- assess the levels of exposure and vulnerability across different urban sectors using quantitative and qualitative indicators.
- develop synthetic indicators of urban risk, organized within a Geographic Information System (GIS) for integrated spatial representation of the phenomena.
- interpret the evolutionary trends of risk factors in relation to territorial transformations and climate change, with reference to future time horizons (2030, 2050, and 2100).
- identify critical areas and potential zones for urban and environmental regeneration, with particular attention to strategic or vulnerable sites targeted for climate-analysis pathways (“Climate Walk”) and for specific focus areas (e.g., the Francesco Rossi barracks).

1.2 Methodological approach

The methodological approach adopted in this study is based on the integration of spatial analysis, geostatistical processing, and cartographic representation of the main territorial, environmental, and climatic indicators.

The research is grounded in a descriptive–analytical method aimed at the systematic survey and mapping of the risk conditions affecting the municipal territory of L’Aquila, through the use of open-data sources and highly reliable geospatial datasets.

The methodological framework combines:

- a deductive perspective, based on scientific literature and international standards for risk analysis (UNDRR, IPCC, EEA);
- an inductive perspective, focused on the direct processing of empirical data and territorial observations through GIS tools and remote sensing.

The methodological process is articulated into three main phases:

1. Data collection and harmonization

- Acquisition and organization of heterogeneous datasets (environmental, climatic, demographic, infrastructural) from institutional sources (Copernicus, EEA, ISPRA, ISTAT, Municipality of L’Aquila).
- Normalization of formats, verification of spatial consistency, and georeferencing within a unified cartographic system (EPSG: 32633 – WGS 84 / UTM zone 33N).

2. Spatial analysis and territorial indicators

- GIS-based elaboration of morphological, environmental, and climatic indicators (building density, soil impermeability, land use, Land Surface Temperature, Sky View Factor, etc.).
- Computation and visualization of interpretative thematic maps, classified according to scales of intensity or vulnerability (low, medium, high).

3. Interpretative synthesis and cartographic representation

- Production of thematic and integrated risk maps, enabling a synoptic reading of the urban system, natural and climatic hazards, and associated vulnerabilities.
- Development of comparative analyses across the different risk components (hydrogeological, seismic, climatic–environmental) to define an overall framework of territorial resilience.

The objective is not the prediction or modelling of future scenarios, but rather the construction of a spatially explicit knowledge base that supports integrated risk assessment and informs urban planning and climate-adaptation policies.

1.3 Data sources and analytical tools

The analysis is based on the combined use of statistical, cartographic, and satellite data from public and open-source platforms, integrated within a GIS environment for spatial representation and modelling.

The main data sources used include:

- ISTAT – demographic, socioeconomic, and census data (Permanent Census of Population and Housing, 2001–2025);
- ISPRA – geological and hydro-geomorphological datasets (landslide inventory, hydraulic and geomorphological hazard);
- Copernicus (ESA/EU) – Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 remotely sensed data for the processing of LST, NDVI, irradiance, and land use classification (Corine Land Cover) for the years 1990–2000–2006–2012–2018;
- EEA – European Environment Agency – climatic and environmental indicators for monitoring temperature variations and green surface dynamics;
- PCC – future climate scenarios and temperature projections (SR 4.5, SR 8.5);
- OpenStreetMap (OSM) – road networks and service infrastructures;
- National Geoportal and Abruzzo Region Geoportal – cartographic bases, orthophotos, and layers of seismic and hydrogeological hazard;
- Open Data L’Aquila – a research project developed by the Gran Sasso Science Institute (GSSI) within the Centre for Urban Informatics and Modelling (CUIM), in collaboration with the University of L’Aquila, the National Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN), the National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology (INGV), the Municipality of L’Aquila, the Special Reconstruction Offices, Fondazione Openpolis and ActionAid.

In addition to the data sources listed above, advanced analytical and simulation tools were employed. Specifically, microclimatic simulations were conducted using ENVI-met 5.7, a three-dimensional software for modelling interactions among atmosphere, soil, buildings, and vegetation in urban environments.

For geometric processing and the construction of three-dimensional models, Rhinoceros 7.0 was used, while parametric environmental analyses were carried out through the Ladybug Tools suite, a set of plug-ins for the Grasshopper (GH) visual scripting environment integrated into Rhinoceros. The Gizmo plug-in for GH was employed for data conversion and georeferencing, ensuring full consistency between the GIS and BIM environments, and enabling a continuous workflow spanning spatial analysis, geometric modelling, and environmental simulation.

2. Data collection and Overall Risk Analysis of the urban context

2.1 Territorial and Historical Framework

Geographical and morphological setting

The city of L’Aquila, capital of the Abruzzo Region, constitutes the main urban and administrative hub of the central Apennine area. The municipal territory covers 473.91 km² and hosts a population of approximately 70,600 inhabitants (ISTAT, 2025), characterized by relatively low population density and a highly dispersed settlement structure.

The historic center is located at 721 m a.s.l. on a hilly relief positioned at the core of the Aquila basin, a wide tectonic depression crossed by the Aterno River, and situated centrally between the Gran Sasso d’Italia massif to the northeast and the Sirente–Velino range to the southwest.

The municipal territory exhibits a pronounced altitudinal variation, with more than half of its surface located above 1,000 m a.s.l., shaping a complex and diversified orographic context. This altitudinal variability significantly influences hydro-geomorphological processes, settlement distribution, and territorial vulnerability to natural hazards. The city lies within a system of intramontane basins bordered by Apennine ridges, with a predominantly carbonate and sedimentary geological substrate, characterized by high seismicity and widespread hydrogeological risk.

From a climatic perspective, L’Aquila presents a temperate-cold Apennine continental climate, with harsh winters, frequent snowfall, and dry summers. Daily and seasonal temperature ranges are particularly pronounced, while the accentuated orography influences precipitation regimes and local wind circulation. These characteristics contribute to the formation of a complex urban microclimate, affecting heat island processes and the distribution of surface temperatures.

Historical and urban development of the city of L’Aquila

The Aquila territory has been inhabited since pre-Roman times by Sabine and Vestine populations. During the Roman age, the city of Amiternum developed along the river of the same name, becoming an important node within the inland road network of central Italy.

The present-day city of L’Aquila was founded in the 13th century as a political and territorial experiment aimed at aggregating the castles of the Aquila basin - among them Amiternum and Forcona - which united to establish a free city with an anti-feudal character. In 1229, permission to found the city was requested from Pope Gregory IX, but the first foundation

was destroyed in 1259 by Manfred of Sicily for political reasons linked to the city’s loyalty to the Papacy. The refoundation took place in 1266 under Charles I of Anjou, adopting a regular and fortified urban layout structured around a system of squares and radial axes.

In 1276, construction of the city walls began, permanently defining the limits of the historic center. A few years later, in 1288, Pietro da Morrone (later Pope Celestine V) commissioned the Basilica of Santa Maria di Collemaggio, which became a symbolic and religious landmark of the city.

Over the following centuries, L’Aquila experienced several destructive earthquakes: those of 1315, 1349 (estimated magnitude 6.5, with approximately 800 victims), 1461, and especially the event of 1703, which profoundly reshaped the urban and architectural fabric. Subsequent reconstruction phases progressively transformed the built morphology, introducing Renaissance, Baroque, and Neoclassical elements, while preserving the original medieval matrix of the urban layout.

Between the 16th and 17th centuries, the city underwent a phase of building consolidation and monumental enrichment, marked by the construction of convents, churches, and noble palaces.

In the 19th century, following the Unification of Italy, L’Aquila embarked on a process of urban modernization: expansion of the road network, redesign of major squares, and introduction of new civic buildings.

Figure 1 – Historical evolution of the city of L’Aquila. Image by F. Colaiori, E.M. Colucci, F. Lentini, S. Proietti

During the Fascist period (1920s–1930s), significant infrastructural interventions and the opening of new road axes modified the spatial relationship between the historic center and the surrounding peripheries. Damage from the Second World War was relatively limited compared to other Italian cities, allowing the historic urban structure to remain largely preserved.

In the post-war period, the city experienced an *extra moenia* urban expansion, with the development of modern residential districts, the implementation of public housing programs, and the construction of a new radial road system. During this phase, the polycentric urban structure that still characterizes L’Aquila became consolidated.

In 1972, the municipal Building Regulation was approved, while in 1979 the General Master Plan (PRG), originally adopted in 1975, came into force. The plan defined the urban structure of the late twentieth century and set guidelines for residential and industrial expansion.

The earthquake of 6 April 2009 (Mw 6.3, intensity VIII–IX MCS) represents a profound historical and territorial rupture for the city: more than 65,000 displaced residents, severe damage to monumental and religious heritage, and a radical rethinking of urban and housing policies. The seismic event led to the creation of new peri-urban settlement centers (the C.A.S.E. Project) and initiated a long, uneven reconstruction process, with significant implications for social cohesion and the morphology of the urban system.

Administrative structure and current planning framework

The Municipality of L’Aquila is today a complex territorial entity, articulated into numerous hamlets and dispersed settlement clusters across its extensive municipal territory. This polycentric configuration represents one of the defining features of the post-earthquake urban structure.

From a planning perspective, the regulatory and operational framework is based on the following key instruments:

- General Regulatory Plan (PRG) approved in 1975 (and enacted in 1979), still formally in force, though undergoing comprehensive revision following the 2009 earthquake and subsequent territorial transformations;
- New PRG under development, initiated by the Municipality of L’Aquila within the broader reconstruction process and the revision of sustainable urban development policies;
- Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (PUMS), a strategic instrument for reorganizing mobility and public transport in an environmentally oriented and resilience-based perspective;
- Reconstruction Plan (PdR) and Urban Regeneration Programs, dedicated to the reconstruction of the historic center and the redevelopment of peripheral districts;
- Regional Landscape Plan (1985) and the new Regional Landscape Plan (PTPR) under preparation, which provide the regulatory framework for the protection of the landscape and environmental values of the Aquila territory.

This evolving planning framework reflects the complexity of the post-seismic urban transition, in which traditional planning tools intersect with policies for resilience, sustainability, and adaptation to natural and climatic risks.

BUILDING FUNCTIONS

CIVIL-WORSHIP BUILDINGS

- Civil building
- Place of worship /Church
- Castle, tower, bell tower
- Building under construction
- City walls

INDUSTRIAL/PRODUCTION BUILDINGS

- Factory
- Agricultural and forestry building, stable, shed
- Shack, hut, precarious structure
- Pressurized tent

INDUSTRIAL STRUCTURES

- Stable greenhouse
- Tank, water tower
- Refinery tank
- Electric substation
- Tank, drinking trough, cistern

Figure 2 – Mapping of building functions. City of L’Aquila and historic center. Image by the authors

2.2 Analysis of the urban and socio-demographic system

Structure of urban fabrics

The urban fabric of L’Aquila is the result of a complex historical stratification, in which the medieval core coexists with successive phases of modern and contemporary expansion. The historic center presents a compact layout organized around a grid of blocks of medieval and Renaissance origin, structured along the main streets converging toward *Corso Vittorio Emanuele II*, the principal axis of the historic city. The urban structure still preserves its original morphology, despite the severe destruction caused by the 6 April 2009 earthquake, which led to the loss or damage of a substantial portion of the architectural and monumental heritage.

Surrounding the ancient core lie residential districts and post-earthquake reconstruction and redevelopment areas, characterized by morphological heterogeneity and discontinuous building density. These patterns reflect differential reconstruction processes and the temporary displacement of the population after 2009. These areas form an evolving urban mosaic, where completed interventions, active construction sites, and spaces awaiting new functions coexist.

The spatial distribution of services and urban infrastructure remains concentrated in specific central districts and major peri-urban areas, generating territorial imbalances that hinder homogeneous functional cohesion. The historic urban fabric is distinguished by its high cultural and architectural value, featuring nationally significant monuments such as the Basilica of Santa Maria di Collemaggio, the Spanish Fortress, the Fontana delle 99 Cannelle, the Cathedral of Saints Maximus and George, Palazzo Centi, Palazzo Margherita, the Municipal Theatre, and numerous churches and convents dating from the 13th to the 18th century.

Overall, the current urban configuration reflects a structural dualism: on one hand, the historic center undergoing a gradual post-earthquake recovery; on the other, a dispersed and polycentric periphery, shaped by emergency housing programs (*Progetto C.A.S.E., M.A.P.*) and settlement dispersion over the last fifteen years. This dual condition significantly influences urban resilience, social cohesion, and the spatial distribution of territorial risk.

Population density and distribution

Demographic analysis reveals a structural decline in the resident population over the past two decades. After a period of relative stability (approximately 73,000 inhabitants until 2008), the 2009 earthquake caused a drastic demographic contraction, with significant population loss in the historic center and in the most severely affected villages (Onna, Roio, Villa Sant’Angelo, Castelnuovo, Tempera, San Gregorio, Paganica).

In the following years, the population stabilized at around 70,600 inhabitants (ISTAT, 2025), without returning to pre-earthquake levels. The average population density - approximately 150 inhabitants/km² - is considerably lower than the national and regional averages, due both to the large municipal area and to settlement fragmentation.

A relevant indicator is the reduction in the average household size, which decreased from 2.49 persons per family in 2008 to 2.10 in 2023, reflecting demographic ageing, declining birth rates, and increasing social vulnerability.

Population distribution shows territorial polarization: concentration in recently developed peri-urban districts and rarefaction in the historic center and internal settlements, where conditions of partial uninhabitability and underuse of the building stock persist.

Socioeconomic structure and social vulnerability

The socioeconomic structure of L’Aquila reflects a post-crisis transition context, in which physical reconstruction is accompanied by processes of social and productive reconfiguration.

The local economy is predominantly tertiary, with a significant presence of public administration, higher education, and healthcare services, followed by the construction and artisanal sectors. The presence of the University of L’Aquila represents an important factor of resilience and innovation, yet it is not sufficient to reverse the trend of youth outmigration and the decline of the resident workforce.

Available socioeconomic indicators (per capita income, employment rate, ageing index, dependency ratio) outline a condition of moderate social vulnerability, with more critical values in peripheral districts and in hillside settlements. The main challenges concern:

- population ageing, with an ageing index higher than the regional average;
- fragmentation of the social fabric, exacerbated by the temporary displacement of households after the earthquake and by the slow reconstitution of community networks;
- uneven access to services, particularly healthcare and education;
- disparities between the historic center and peripheral areas in terms of infrastructure, mobility, and employment opportunities.

Within this framework, social vulnerability intersects with physical and environmental vulnerability, amplifying overall risk and underscoring the need for integrated policies of urban regeneration and socio-economic inclusion.

Condition of the building stock and post-earthquake reconstruction processes

The recovery capacity of the architectural and monumental heritage is a key component of L’Aquila’s urban resilience. Assessments conducted in the immediate aftermath of the 6 April 2009 earthquake showed that just over half of public and private buildings remained usable, whereas approximately one-third presented structural damage of varying severity. The cultural heritage - comprising churches, historic palaces, and monumental complexes - was particularly affected, with more than 50% of buildings declared unusable.

According to *Open Data Ricostruzione* (2024), the municipal territory includes 360 reconstruction interventions, of which 54% have been completed (195 worksites). Eighty-one interventions concern the historic center, yet only one quarter of them have been finalized (20). This uneven pace of progress - linked to administrative complexity and the fragmented nature of recovery processes - continues to hinder the full functional and social revival of the city.

The slow reconstruction process, especially within the historic core, has produced physical voids and discontinuities of use that affect territorial cohesion, access to services, and the reactivation of local economies. These conditions represent a critical challenge for medium-term integrated planning and urban regeneration.

PUBLIC SERVICES

- Istruzione
- Culto
- Cultura
- Sanità
- Amministrazione

- Rete stradale
- Rete ferroviaria

0 250 500 m

Figure 3 – Mapping of services and the road–railway network. City of L’Aquila and historic center. Image by the authors

2.3 Analysis of infrastructure and services

Mobility and transport networks

The urban and territorial mobility system of L’Aquila is structured around a radial and polycentric configuration, in which the main road connections link the city with its outlying settlements and neighboring municipalities, while maintaining a strong dependence on the A24 motorway (Rome–L’Aquila–Teramo).

The A24 constitutes the strategic axis connecting L’Aquila with the Rome metropolitan area and the Adriatic corridor. However, its infrastructural vulnerability - due to the ageing condition of several viaducts and tunnels, as well as the complex orographic context - represents a critical point for safety and continuity of transport in the event of seismic or landslide-related events.

The secondary road network, including State Roads 17 and 80, links the urban core with the main peripheral settlements (Pettino, Coppito, Paganica, Bazzano, Roio, Preturo), but shows heterogeneous maintenance conditions, steep gradients, and winter-related criticalities that can compromise accessibility during adverse weather conditions.

The road network of L’Aquila also presents several *urban discontinuities* that fragment spatial and pedestrian connectivity:

- Viale Gran Sasso interrupts the spatial relationship between the Parco del Castello and the main pedestrian boulevard;
- Viale Alcide De Gasperi creates a break within the Torrione district;
- Viale della Croce Rossa separates the historic center from adjacent districts, limiting integration between different urban areas;
- Viale Duca degli Abruzzi terminates at the Belvedere Bridge, which has been unusable since the 2009 earthquake, producing a significant discontinuity in the road system surrounding the historic core.

Regarding public transport, a distinction must be made between urban and extra-urban services. Urban public transport (TPL) is managed by AMA S.p.A. L’AQUILA, a company fully owned by the Municipality, which operates intra-municipal routes serving both the city and its peripheral settlements. TUA S.p.A., instead, provides extra-urban, provincial, and regional services. Overall, public transport - both urban and regional - has been strengthened in the post-earthquake period, yet remains insufficient in terms of frequency and coverage, particularly in peripheral areas.

Demand for public transport is relatively low: only 12% of residents hold a TPL pass, while the motorization rate is 80 cars per 100 inhabitants (ISTAT, 2023), a value higher than both the Italian (70) and European (57) averages. According to the 2019 ISTAT mobility survey, 78%

of urban trips and 94% of extra-urban trips are made by private vehicle, contributing to congestion, increased emissions, and reduced accessibility to central areas.

Recently, as part of the Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan (PUMS), several interventions have been initiated, including the extension of 30-km/h zones in residential and school areas, the enlargement of limited-traffic zones (ZTL), and the gradual development of the urban cycling network, which is currently scarce and highly discontinuous. These measures aim to reduce vehicle speeds, improve road safety, and decrease climate-altering emissions.

The railway system, served by the Terni–Rieti–L’Aquila–Sulmona line, plays a marginal role in daily commuting due to its low service frequency and single-track, non-electrified infrastructure. The “Giuliana Tamburro” Parks Airport (Preturo) currently operates exclusively for logistical support and civil protection purposes.

Overall, L’Aquila’s mobility network exhibits limitations in terms of accessibility, redundancy, and resilience, particularly considering the territory’s morphology and the extensive size of the municipal area. Connectivity analysis highlights travel times above the national average for reaching essential services from the most remote peripheral settlements.

Distribution of essential services (healthcare, education, emergency response)

The network of essential services in L’Aquila exhibits a strongly polarized hierarchical structure. The main healthcare, educational, and emergency-response functions are concentrated in the urban core, while the outlying settlements and mountain hamlets display significant functional dispersion and longer access times to basic services.

- **Healthcare:** the San Salvatore Hospital serves as the primary health facility for the entire provincial territory, supported by outpatient centers and peripheral health districts. However, limited accessibility from certain settlements and the lack of direct connections reduce the overall efficiency of the emergency-care network.
- **Education:** the educational system is organized into several distributed school complexes, although the school network has undergone consolidation processes after the 2009 earthquake, with a reduction in active buildings in the more marginal areas. The University of L’Aquila and the Gran Sasso Science Institute, through their decentralized campuses, play a strategic role in sustaining high-level urban functions;
- **Emergency and Civil Protection Services:** the territory benefits from an articulated network of facilities (Fire Brigade, Civil Protection, Red Cross), strengthened after 2009; however, the infrastructural vulnerability of some facilities and the wide territorial dispersion call for continuous updating of emergency plans and risk-management strategies.

The concentration of services within the central urban core, combined with limited functional integration with the peripheral settlements, increases territorial inequality and constitutes a systemic vulnerability within the overall risk analysis framework.

Complementary services

Beyond essential services, the city offers a range of complementary services that contribute to urban quality of life and social resilience. These include:

- Sports and recreational services, mainly located in the urban core, including gyms, swimming pools, and multifunctional facilities, some of which have been rebuilt or seismically upgraded after 2009;
- Cultural and museum services, such as the MuNDA – National Museum of Abruzzo, the MuSPAC – Experimental Museum of Contemporary Art, MAXXI L’Aquila, the Teatro Comunale, Teatro Zeta, Palazzo dell’Emiciclo, and Palazzo dei Nobili, all of which host cultural and exhibition activities of national relevance. An additional key facility is the *Auditorium del Parco*, designed by architect Renzo Piano and inaugurated in 2012 within the Parco del Castello, conceived as a symbol of post-earthquake renewal and as a major venue for contemporary cultural production and dissemination.
- Administrative and institutional services, concentrated in the historic center (Palazzo Margherita, municipal headquarters; Palazzo dell’Emiciclo, seat of the Regional Council), as well as in the areas of Viale Aldo Moro and Via Leonardo da Vinci, which host prominent public and regional offices;
- Commercial and productive services, primarily located along the main urban access routes and in the areas of Bazzano, Pile, and Campo di Pile, where major commercial and logistical hubs of provincial significance are situated;
- Energy and environmental services, managed by ASM and Gran Sasso Acqua, ensuring water distribution and waste collection, with generally good performance levels but localized vulnerabilities during hydrogeological emergencies.

Although these services cannot be classified strictly as “essential,” they constitute functional components that are crucial for territorial resilience, as they contribute to the capacity of the urban system to maintain livability, social cohesion, and operational continuity even under stress conditions.

Cultural resilience and territorial attractiveness

Despite the challenges and the prolonged reconstruction phase, L’Aquila is progressively reasserting its role as a cultural and identity hub of central Italy.

Its designation as Italian Capital of Culture 2026, with the project “*L’Aquila. Città Multiverso*”, represents an acknowledgment of the city’s trajectory of rebirth fifteen years after the earthquake. The candidacy is structured around the four strategic pillars of the New European Agenda for Culture - social cohesion, health and well-being, creativity and innovation, and socio-environmental sustainability - thus outlining an integrated vision of urban development grounded in culture, inclusion, and sustainability.

The tourism sector shows signs of structural recovery: after the decline caused by the pandemic, visitor numbers in 2022 returned to 2018 levels, with 196 active accommodation facilities, mainly concentrated in the city. The museum and cultural institutions within the functional urban area - seven in the Municipality of L’Aquila and one in the nearby Municipality of Fossa - recorded over 60,000 annual visitors, confirming a positive trend in the use of cultural heritage.

These data highlight the city’s capacity for attraction and regeneration, supported by its extraordinary architectural and monumental heritage. If properly enhanced, the network of cultural assets can become a driver of sustainable socio-economic development, promoting social cohesion, diversification of the urban economy, and strengthening L’Aquila’s role at the national level as a laboratory of cultural resilience and innovation.

GREEN AREAS

URBAN AND PERI-URBAN GREEN

- | | |
|--|--|
| Olive groves |
| Vineyards |
| Trees |
| Orchards | |

Figure 4 – Mapping of green areas. City of L’Aquila and historic center. Image by the authors

2.4 Analysis of the biophysical and environmental system

Morphology and geology

The municipal territory of L’Aquila features a complex and highly articulated morphology, shaped by the interaction between Apennine tectonic dynamics and geomorphological processes linked to fluvial and karst modeling.

The city is located in the heart of the central Apennines, within the so-called Aquila basin, a wide tectonic depression bounded by carbonate mountain ridges and surrounded by some of the highest mountain chains of peninsular Italy: the Gran Sasso d’Italia massif to the northeast, and the Ocre–Cagno and Sirente–Velino ranges to the southwest.

The average elevation of the municipal territory is approximately 720 m a.s.l., but the altitudinal range is considerable: from just under 600 m a.s.l. in the Aterno valley floor to over 2,600 m a.s.l. in the highest mountain areas of the Gran Sasso massif. The maximum elevation within the municipal boundaries is located in the area of Pizzo d’Intermesoli, reaching 2,635 m a.s.l., underscoring the markedly mountainous character of L’Aquila’s orographic structure. More than half of the municipal surface lies above 1,000 m a.s.l., outlining a high-altitude territorial system characterized by significant microclimatic and morphological variations.

The hydrographic network is dominated by the Aterno River, the main drainage axis of the basin, which crosses the municipal area from west to southeast. Its secondary tributaries and minor drainage lines - often ephemeral - contribute to shaping the slopes and generating diffuse erosion processes.

From a geomorphological perspective, the city stands on an isolated hilly relief overlooking the valley floor, characterized by moderate slopes and a substrate composed of incoherent sediments and alternating carbonate formations. This position provides a certain degree of protection from flooding phenomena but does not eliminate localized risks related to slope instability and differential subsidence associated with alluvial deposits.

Land Use and Green Surface Distribution

Methodology

To analyze the territorial structure and the evolution of land use in the Municipality of L’Aquila and its surrounding mountain areas, the CORINE Land Cover (CLC) dataset from the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service was employed. CLC provides comprehensive and standardized coverage of the European territory, organized into 44 land-cover classes distributed across three hierarchical levels (5 classes at Level 1, 15 at Level 2, and 44 at Level 3), enabling consistent comparative analysis across EU Member States.

The study examined the five main CLC reference years available - 1990, 2000, 2006, 2012, and 2018 - to assess the temporal evolution of territorial transformations. Vector files were

downloaded from the Copernicus Open Access Hub, processed in a GIS environment (QGIS 3.42), and clipped within a 15 km radius buffer.

Subsequently, polygons in each layer were classified according to the five Level-1 CLC macro-categories:

- Artificial surfaces;
- Agricultural areas;
- Forest and semi-natural areas;
- Wetlands;
- Water bodies.

Following the CLC classification, the area of each polygon in the vector layer was calculated. Using the field calculator tool, an “Area” field was created in the attribute table. The Statistics tool was then used to calculate the percentage share of each land-use class relative to the total analyzed surface.

Temporal evolution of territorial transformations

The diachronic analysis of CORINE Land Cover (CLC) data for 1990, 2000, 2006, 2012, and 2018 made it possible to reconstruct the evolution of land use within the municipal territory of L’Aquila and the surrounding mountain areas, with particular attention to patterns of land artificialization and changes affecting rural and natural landscapes.

During the 1990–2000 period, the most significant increase in artificial surfaces is observed, with a notable expansion of continuous and discontinuous urban fabric, infrastructures, and productive areas. This phase reflects the progressive urbanization of the margins of the city and the settlement dispersion associated with the tertiarization processes and infrastructural development initiated in the 1990s.

From 2000 to 2006, artificial surface expansion shows relative stabilization, indicating a balance between the saturation of buildable areas and a slowdown in new urbanization processes. Transformations occurring in this period are mainly concentrated in valley-floor agricultural areas, where limited conversions to low-density residential and productive functions take place.

In 2012, a new localized increase in artificial surfaces is detected, primarily linked to the construction of new post-earthquake neighborhoods following the 2009 seismic event. The Progetto C.A.S.E. developments and areas temporarily assigned to emergency housing and services contribute to increased artificial coverage, especially in the western and southwestern sectors of the territory. This phase marks a structural change in settlement distribution, resulting in greater fragmentation of the urban fabric and increased soil impermeabilization.

In the 2012–2018 interval, the phenomenon tends toward stabilization, with limited and localized transformations. Urban expansion slows, yet the artificial areas developed in the post-earthquake context persist, maintaining a discontinuous and dispersed settlement pattern.

A notable peculiarity in the 1990 CLC dataset is the presence of a large area classified as artificial surface at the location of Lake Campotosto, situated north of the municipal territory. This anomaly is interpretable as the effect of a temporary lowering or drainage of the artificial basin during the satellite acquisition, linked to hydraulic management of the three dams constructed between the 1930s and 1940s. It is therefore likely that exposed lakebed surfaces were erroneously classified as artificial land, although the site corresponds to a hydroelectric reservoir rather than an urbanized area.

Overall, the temporal analysis highlights a moderate yet significant increase in land artificialization between 1990 and 2012, followed by a recent stabilization phase. In parallel, agricultural and forested areas retain a predominant role, outlining a territorial system that remains largely natural but increasingly affected by ecological fragmentation and a progressive reduction of landscape continuity in valley-floor and peri-urban areas.

CORINE LAND COVER

- 1. Artificial Surfaces
- 2. Agricultural areas
- 3. Forest and seminatural areas
- 5. Water bodies

- Municipal administrative boundary
- 20km buffer

Figure 5 – Corine Land Cover 1990. Large-scale view. Image by the authors

CORINE LAND COVER

- 1. Artificial Surfaces
- 2. Agricultural areas
- 3. Forest and seminatural areas
- 5. Water bodies

- Municipal administrative boundary
- 20km buffer

Figure 6 – Corine Land Cover 2000. Large-scale view. Image by the authors

CORINE LAND COVER

- 1. Artificial Surfaces
- 2. Agricultural areas
- 3. Forest and seminatural areas
- 5. Water bodies

0 2,5 5 10 km

- Municipal administrative boundary
- 20km buffer

Figure 7 – Corine Land Cover 2006. Large-scale view. Image by the authors

CORINE LAND COVER

- 1. Artificial Surfaces
- 2. Agricultural areas
- 3. Forest and seminatural areas
- 5. Water bodies

- Municipal administrative boundary
- 20km buffer

Figure 8 – Corine Land Cover 2012. Large-scale view. Image by the authors

CORINE LAND COVER

- 1. Artificial Surfaces
- 2. Agricultural areas
- 3. Forest and seminatural areas
- 5. Water bodies

Figure 9 – Corine Land Cover 2018. Large-scale view. Image by the authors

Results of the territorial analysis

The 2018 CLC analysis shows that the municipal territory of L’Aquila is dominated by forested areas and semi-natural environments, forming a continuous ring along the Apennine slopes surrounding the basin. The prevailing classes are:

- Broad-leaved forests (3.1.1);
- Natural grasslands and high-altitude pastures (3.2.1);
- Transitional woodland–shrub vegetation (3.2.4).

These land-cover types occupy the majority of the municipal surface, ensuring essential ecological functions such as microclimate regulation, soil protection, CO₂ capture and sequestration, and biodiversity conservation.

In the valley floor and inner basin areas, an agricultural mosaic is present, characterized by non-irrigated arable land (2.1.1), complex cultivation patterns (2.4.2), and agricultural areas interspersed with natural elements (2.4.3). These zones form a transitional belt between the urban fabric and the forested mountain systems, maintaining an important ecological and landscape buffer function.

Artificial surfaces (1.1 and 1.2) are mainly concentrated within the Aquila basin along the Aterno River axis, where the main urban core and satellite settlements of Coppito, Pettino, Pile, Bazzano, and Paganica are located. These settlements define a polycentric urban model, with continuous built-up areas in the most consolidated districts and discontinuous patterns in peri-urban sectors shaped by recent post-earthquake reconstruction.

Production and service areas (1.2.1) are situated near major infrastructure nodes and along the valley-floor road corridors, particularly in Campo di Pile and Bazzano.

At a closer scale, the overlay of built-up layers with the road and rail networks indicates the highest density within the historic center and its immediate expansions, classified as continuous urban fabric (1.1.1). Surrounding this core, a ring of discontinuous urban fabric (1.1.2) merges into the agricultural mosaic and remaining arable land patches, forming the urban–rural transition zone.

CORINE LAND COVER

1. Artificial Surfaces

- 1.1.1. Continuous urban fabric
- 1.1.2. Discontinuous urban fabric
- 1.2.1. Industrial or commercial units
- 1.2.4. Airports
- 1.3.1. Airports
- 1.4.1. Green urban areas
- 1.4.2. Sport and leisure facilities

2. Agricultural areas

- 2.1.1. Non-irrigated arable land
- 2.3.1. Pastures
- 2.4.1. annual crops associated with permanent crops
- 2.4.2. Complex cultivation patterns
- 2.4.3. Land principally occupied by agriculture

- Municipal administrative boundary
- 20km buffer

3. Forest and seminatural areas

- 3.1.1. Broad-leaved forest
- 3.1.2. Coniferous forest
- 3.1.3. Mixed forest
- 3.2.1. Natural grassland
- 3.2.2. Moors and heathland
- 3.2.4. Transitional woodland shrub
- 3.3.2. Bare rock
- 3.3.3. Sparsely vegetated areas

4. Water bodies

- 5.1.2. Water bodies

Figure 10 – Complete Corine Land Cover Classification 2018. Large-scale view. Image by the authors

Percentage and distribution of green areas

The analysis of green and natural surfaces reveals a marked urban–rural–natural gradient:

- High compactness of the built environment within the urban core;
- Deconcentration and discontinuity along the peripheral margins;
- Rapid transition toward forest cover on the surrounding mountain slopes.

Within the boundaries of the historic center, green areas are limited and highly fragmented, consisting primarily of small gardens, internal courtyards, and minor urban parks. In this area, approximately 70% of the surface is urbanized, 15% is green, and 10% is agricultural or fallow. This scarcity of open spaces results in low ecological permeability and a reduced microclimatic mitigation capacity, contributing to urban heat island effects and increasing overall environmental vulnerability.

In peri-urban neighborhoods and adjacent zones, several urban and peri-urban parks provide landscape quality and public recreational opportunities, including Parco del Castello - a site of major historical and symbolic value - Parco del Sole, and Parco del Torrione, which also function as ecological connectors.

The prevailing native vegetation species include *Fagus sylvatica* (European beech), *Acer pseudoplatanus* (sycamore maple), *Quercus pubescens* (downy oak), *Sorbus domestica* (service tree), *Populus alba* (white poplar), and *Juglans regia* (walnut), reflecting the typical floristic composition of medium- and high-altitude Apennine ecosystems.

Overall forest cover (CLC categories 3.1 and 3.2) exceeds 60% of the municipal territory, providing substantial ecological and landscape value. However, land consumption has increased since 1990, primarily due to the construction of post-earthquake residential districts, new infrastructure, and industrial areas in the valley floor.

Although moderate in absolute terms, this process has led to progressive landscape fragmentation and a reduction in ecological connectivity between natural and agricultural areas. Remote sensing analyses indicate that the remaining green corridors are primarily located along the Aterno River and the slopes connecting the city to the Gran Sasso and Monti della Laga National Park, representing priority elements for climate adaptation and environmental mitigation strategies.

Figure 11 – Complete Corine Land Cover 2018 classification. City of L’Aquila and historic center. Image by the authors

Interpretative summary

Land use within the Municipality of L’Aquila reflects a polycentric territorial system characterized by high environmental heterogeneity. Anthropogenic pressure is concentrated within the central basin, while peripheral and mountainous areas retain a high degree of naturalness.

The limited availability of green spaces within the urban fabric, combined with increasing soil sealing in newly developed districts, constitutes a factor of environmental vulnerability, amplifying risks related to the urban microclimate and the loss of biodiversity.

Conversely, the continuity of forested areas and the proximity to the natural systems of the Apennines represent a significant potential for ecological and landscape resilience. This potential should be enhanced through integrated planning tools (PRG, PTPR, PAESC) and through interventions aimed at ecological restoration and environmental rebalancing.

3. Analysis of natural and climate-related risks

3.1 Hydrogeological risk

Hydrographic system and flood-prone areas

The municipal territory of L’Aquila is characterized by a hydrographic network that, while not as extensive as those found in large lowland basins, presents significant elements of hydraulic and hydrogeological hazard. The most prominent watercourse is the Aterno–Pescara River (commonly referred to simply as “Aterno”), which traverses the Aquila basin and contributes to drainage across the central Apennine catchment.

Main hydrographic characteristics

- The Aterno River originates in the Monti della Laga, flows west–east through the Aquila basin, and features a drainage basin of considerable size ($\approx 3,190 \text{ km}^2$ within the Abruzzo region).
- One of its major right-bank tributaries is the Raio River, with a catchment area of approximately 230 km^2 entirely within the Province of L’Aquila. The confluence between the Raio and the Aterno, located near the Pile district, is identified as a particularly critical area for flood hazard and sediment accumulation.
- The morphological substrate and the relatively wide basin favor rapid runoff during intense precipitation events, due to the moderate slope and the presence of alluvial deposits in the central portion of the basin.

Flood-prone areas and vulnerability conditions

Within the municipal boundaries, the industrial and commercial area of Pile has been explicitly identified in local reports as “*subject to high flood risk*” and in need of structural interventions along the river system.

Analyses conducted as part of the “*Hydraulic Compatibility Assessment of the Aterno River*” indicate that the area falls within the flood hazard zones defined by the *Piano per l’Assetto Idrogeologico* (PAI – Hydrogeological Plan) of the Aterno–Pescara basin.

Key vulnerability factors include:

- the concentration of productive and residential functions in the valley floor along the river axis, historically associated with high hydraulic risk zones;
- increasing soil sealing in urban and peri-urban areas as a result of post-earthquake development, which reduces infiltration capacity and accelerates surface runoff;

- the basin topography, which - while mitigating some primary flow dynamics - favors the accumulation of runoff and the triggering of sheet flow or ponding in low-lying areas;
- the presence of critical infrastructures (industrial areas, road networks, utilities) in close proximity to the river, which raises the potential damage in the event of flooding.

Regulatory tools and planning framework

The Central Apennine River Basin Authority has adopted the *Piano per l’Assetto Idrogeologico* (PAI), which identifies river corridors characterized by varying levels of flood hazard and establishes land-use restrictions and required infrastructural adaptations. The Abruzzo Region and the Municipality of L’Aquila have integrated additional technical instruments (e.g., hydraulic compatibility studies) to support flood hazard assessment and mitigation.

Future perspectives and scenarios

Under climate-change scenarios that foresee more frequent extreme precipitation events, flood-prone areas along the Aterno River and its tributaries may be exposed to more frequent and more intense flooding. The combined effects of rapid runoff, mobile sediments, and increased soil sealing highlight the need for strengthened infrastructural planning, hydraulic protection measures, and early-warning systems.

HYDROGEOLOGICAL RISK

HAZARD CLASSIFICATION

- R1 | Moderate risk
- R2 | Medium risk
- R3 | High risk
- R4 | Very high risk

- Municipal administrative boundary
- 20km buffer

Figure 12 – Hydrogeological risk. Large-scale. Image by the authors

HYDROGEOLOGICAL RISK

HAZARD CLASSIFICATION

- R1 | Moderate risk
- R2 | Medium risk
- R3 | High risk
- R4 | Very high risk

Figure 13 – Hydrogeological risk. City of L’Aquila and historic center. Image by the authors

3.2 Landslide risk

Geomorphological dynamics and slope instability

The territory of L’Aquila and the broader Aquila basin is strongly characterized by mountainous and hilly slopes with moderate to steep gradients, heterogeneous lithological substrates, and Quaternary deposits frequently affected by instability.

The main predisposing factors for slope instability include:

- Alpine–Apennine morphology: the carbonate reliefs of the Gran Sasso d’Italia massif, the Sirente–Velino range, and the Ocre–Cagno mountains surrounding the Aquila basin.
- Differentiated lithologies: massive carbonates (limestones and dolomites) in higher areas and alluvial/colluvial deposits in the basin and lower slopes, increasing the likelihood of both shallow and deep-seated landslides.
- High altitudinal range: half of the municipal territory lies above 1,000 m a.s.l., with slope environments strongly influenced by gravitational processes and surface drainage.
- High precipitation and steep gradients: intense rainfall in mountainous contexts promotes rapid water accumulation in soils and deposits, reducing material cohesion and increasing the potential for slope failure.

These conditions shape a geomorphological setting in which landslides - sliding, flowing, shallow or deep-seated - represent a significant component of territorial risk.

Evidence and regional data

According to ISPRA’s national landslide inventory (with specific reference to Abruzzo), a significant presence of landslide phenomena is documented across the region, including zones classified as having high or very high landslide hazard. Within the municipality of L’Aquila, the share of population residing in areas of high hazard is below 1%.

At the regional level, approximately 15.4% of Abruzzo’s territory falls within “high or very high landslide hazard” classes. These data indicate that, although the urbanized portions of L’Aquila may be less directly exposed than other regional areas, the potential for instability remains concrete - particularly along slopes and in less urbanized sectors of the municipal territory.

Critical areas and local dynamics

Several zones within the L’Aquila municipal area are particularly sensitive to slope instability dynamics:

- Slopes surrounding the Aquila basin: hilly and mountainous areas near the urban core (e.g., Monteluco–Roio, Collefracido) feature unstable colluvial deposits and natural scarps prone to change under soil saturation conditions.
- Alluvial and colluvial deposits: valley-floor areas and zones adjacent to the Aterno River display differential instability and low-cohesion materials despite the partial buffering effect of the hydraulic system.
- Post-earthquake settlement expansion: new residential districts and infrastructures built after the 2009 earthquake - particularly in peri-urban areas with steeper slopes or recent deposits - may have increased vulnerability through morphology alteration, additional anthropogenic load, and modified drainage conditions.
- Vegetation discontinuities: deforestation, anthropogenic disturbance, or wildfires reduce slope cohesion and increase susceptibility to debris flows and shallow landslides.

LANDSLIDE HAZARD

HAZARD CLASSIFICATION

- P1 | Moderate hazard
- P2 | High hazard
- P3 | Very high hazard

- Municipal administrative boundary
- 20km buffer

Figure 14 – Landslide risk. Broad-scale view. Image by the authors

LANDSLIDE HAZARD

HAZARD CLASSIFICAZIONE

- P1 | Moderate hazard
- P2 | High hazard
- P3 | Very high hazard

0 250 500 m

Figure 15 – Landslide risk. City of L'Aquila and historic center. Image by the authors

3.3 Seismic risk

Historical seismicity and building vulnerability

The territory of L’Aquila falls entirely within Seismic Zone 1, the highest seismic hazard category defined by Ordinance PCM No. 3274/2003 and confirmed by subsequent updates of the Italian Civil Protection Department. The area is characterized by active and frequent seismicity, including high-magnitude events that confirm the persistent activity of extensional fault systems along the western margin of the Aquila basin.

The city lies along the L’Aquila–Paganica–San Demetrio normal fault system, extending for more than 25 km with a predominant NW–SE orientation. This structure, part of the broader seismogenic district of the central Apennines, represents one of the major crustal deformation elements in the Abruzzo region and is responsible for most of the historical seismicity.

Historical seismicity

L’Aquila has one of the most extensive seismic records in Italy. Among the most significant events:

- 3 December 1315, $M \approx 6.0$ – first historically documented earthquake with severe damage to the city walls;
- 9 September 1349, $M \approx 6.5$ – extensive destruction of the city and of many settlements in the basin;
- 26 November 1461, $M \approx 6.4$ – widespread damage and subsequent Renaissance-period reconstruction;
- 2 February 1703, $M \approx 6.7$ – the most devastating earthquake in L’Aquila’s history, which destroyed most of the built fabric and shaped the later Baroque urban form;
- 6 April 2009, $M = 6.3$ – the most destructive recent event, with severe impacts at regional scale.

Mapping of recent seismicity

As part of this research, a geospatial map of earthquakes with magnitude >3.5 recorded from 1985 to the present was produced, using INGV-ISIDe datasets (<http://opendata.regione.abruzzo.it/content/scosse-di-terremoto-nella-regione-abruzzo>) and processed in QGIS 3.42.

The resulting map shows a concentration of seismic events along the south-western margin of the Aquila basin, consistent with the trace of the main fault segment activated in 2009. Additional clusters of lower-magnitude seismicity appear to the north-west and in the south-eastern sector, indicating a complex and still active fault network.

EARTHQUAKE SHOCKS (M>3.5) SINCE 1985

MAGNITUDE (M)

3,5 6

0 2,5 5 10 km

 Municipal administrative boundary
 20km buffer

Figure 16 – Seismic risk. Large-scale view. Image by the authors

EARTHQUAKE SHOCKS (M>3.5) SINCE 1985

MAGNITUDE (M)

3,5 6

0 250 500 m

- Buildings
- Road network
- Railway
- Urban walls
- Historical center

Figure 17 – Seismic risk. City of L'Aquila and historic center. Image by the authors

3.4 Climate and environmental risks

Land Surface Temperature (LST)

LAND SURFACE TEMPERATURE

LAND SURFACE TEMPERATURE [°C]

52.14 16.31

0 2,5 5 10 km

 Municipal administrative boundary
 20km buffer

Figure 1 - Land Surface Temperature. Large-scale view. Image by the authors

The map illustrates the Land Surface Temperature (LST) of the urban and peri-urban area of L’Aquila, computed for 18 July 2024 and 16 July 2025. The satellite images were reprojected into EPSG:32633 (WGS 84 / UTM Zone 33N) and converted to degrees Celsius, yielding values ranging from approximately 16.3°C to 52.1°C. Higher temperatures (shown in red

tones) are concentrated in the Aquila basin and along urbanised and agricultural valley floors, especially over mineral surfaces, asphalt, impermeable roofs, and dry soils, where the combination of low soil moisture and the high thermal inertia of materials generates significant heat accumulation.

Lower temperatures (blue tones) occur along the surrounding forested and mountainous areas, where vegetation cover and orographic shading promote heat dissipation. Minimum values also appear near water bodies, humid valley floors, and shaded slopes.

A distinct valley–mountain thermal gradient is observable, modulated by both elevation and aspect: at equal altitude, south-west–facing slopes are consistently warmer than north-east–facing ones due to greater solar exposure.

The map serves as a planning support tool for urban climate adaptation, identifying priority areas for interventions related to urban cooling, soil permeabilisation, tree planting, and the adoption of cool or green roofs. However, for a more comprehensive assessment of thermal comfort and heat vulnerability, LST must be integrated with additional environmental indicators such as NDVI, soil impermeability, and high-resolution local microclimatic observations.

Thermal anomalies and Urban Heat Island (UHI)

Context and climatic relevance

One of the most significant climate-related risks is the Urban Heat Island (UHI), particularly its summer manifestation at ground level, known as Surface Urban Heat Island (SUHI). In L’Aquila, this effect can raise temperatures in central urban areas by up to 12°C compared to the surrounding rural zones.

As part of the MIRIFICUS project (Monitoring reforestation interventions for urban heat islands via satellite), a study coordinated by the Institute of Bioeconomy of the National Research Council (CNR-Ibe), in collaboration with ISPRA, analysed SUHI intensity in Italy’s twenty regional capitals using NASA and Copernicus summer data from 2013 to 2023. The results, published in *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment* (Albini et al., 2025), show that heat island intensity is strongly influenced by the topography of cities, in addition to the presence of impermeable artificial surfaces.

Cities with complex orography and extensive peri-urban green areas - such as L’Aquila, Genoa, Turin, Trieste and Trento - display more pronounced thermal differences between central and peripheral zones compared to cities on flat terrain (Rome, Milan, Naples, Florence), where UHI intensity is generally lower.

Building on these findings, a dedicated analysis was carried out for L’Aquila to precisely map summer thermal anomalies and to clearly distinguish genuinely urban thermal effects from those driven by orography, ensuring that the typical altimetric differences of the Apennine context were not mistakenly interpreted as urban anomalies.

Methodology

Multispectral and thermal data from Landsat 8–9 OLI/TIRS Collection 2 Level-2, with a spatial resolution of 30 m (<https://doi.org/10.5066/P9OGBGM6>), were used for this analysis. These datasets are already atmospherically corrected and suitable for quantitative applications without requiring additional complex preprocessing. Image selection was focused on time windows corresponding to heat waves (HW) over the last two years, based on data availability and quality. The analysis was performed for two specific dates: 18 July 2024 and 16 July 2025.

Processing in QGIS included reprojection into EPSG:32633 (WGS 84 / UTM Zone 33N) and the calculation of Land Surface Temperature (LST) in degrees Celsius. Mean values were obtained using the GRASS r.series tool.

Since L’Aquila is not included in the JRC dataset of Functional Urban Areas (FUA), due to its highly fragmented settlement pattern, the municipal boundary was adopted as a proxy. A 20 km buffer was generated from the centroid of this polygon and used to clip the satellite images. Thermal anomalies were calculated by comparing median urban LST values with those of vegetated non-urban areas located between 10 and 20 km from the centroid.

A crucial methodological step involved excluding vegetated reference areas located more than ± 300 m above or below the city’s mean elevation (700 m a.s.l.). In a mountainous context such as L’Aquila, even moderate elevation differences have a strong impact on surface temperature due to thermal lapse rates and microclimatic variability. Including such areas would introduce systematic bias, attributing to the UHI thermal variations caused only by orography. Restricting the comparison to surfaces at similar relative elevation isolates the genuinely urban component of the thermal anomaly, ensuring that measured differences reflect urbanisation rather than altitude-driven gradients.

This process allowed the identification and analysis of thermal variations within the urban core of L’Aquila.

Finally, to interpret the relationship between thermal anomalies and anthropogenic features, the LST raster was overlaid with the road network and the built-up area of the historic centre, obtained from the Geoportal of the Abruzzo Region and from Open Data L’Aquila.

Workflow

1. Data selection and download:
 - a. Landsat 8
 - b. CLC
2. FUA – Definition of the study area
 - a. FUA identification (= municipal boundary of L’Aquila)
 - b. Calculation of the FUA centroid
 - c. Creation of a 20 km buffer from the centroid

- d. Creation of a 10 km buffer from the centroid
3. Image extraction
 - a. Use of the 20 km buffer as the clipping area for LST and CLC
4. Calculation of land cover distribution and LST
 - a. Conversion of LST from Kelvin to Celsius¹
 - b. Creation of a circular ring (10–20 km) around the FUA
 - c. Extraction of LST and CLC within the 10–20 km ring
 - d. Identification of points farthest from the edges of “vegetation” polygons (CLC classes)
 - e. Selection of points at least 250 m inside the ring buffer
 - f. Selection of points within ± 300 m of the city’s mean elevation (700 m a.s.l.)
 - g. Extraction of LST values from rasters at the selected “pins”
 - h. Calculation of the average LST of non-urban reference areas to establish the baseline surface temperature
5. Thermal anomaly analysis
 - a. Calculation of temperature differences (ΔT) between each pixel and the mean values of the non-urban areas
 - b. Definition of ΔT as the urban thermal anomaly

Results

The historic centre of L’Aquila is characterised by low tree cover and a high density of impermeable surfaces such as asphalt, stone, and concrete, which absorb and retain heat. Conversely, the suburban and rural areas - greener and less built-up - provide substantial cooling. This strong thermal contrast amplifies the Surface Urban Heat Island (SUHI) effect. The mountainous morphology of the city, which naturally limits horizontal expansion and the availability of green spaces in the core urban area, further exacerbates these conditions. The thermal anomaly map shows that, relative to the mean temperature of the surrounding non-urban vegetated areas, the most urbanised zones exhibit positive thermal anomalies up to $+12^{\circ}\text{C}$.

In contrast, areas classified as “Forest” under the Corine Land Cover (CLC) system show negative anomalies down to -21°C , reflecting the strong cooling capacity of dense vegetation.

¹ Since the satellite image contains digital numbers, these digital numbers must be converted into temperature values using the following equation:
Raster Calculator expression for raster file conversion = (“Satellite file name” * 0.00341802) + 149.0 (additive factor) – 273.15 (for the conversion from Kelvin to Celsius).

Open agricultural areas and forested slopes tend to mitigate thermal anomalies, while urbanised valley floors and infrastructural plateaus emerge as distinct and widespread hotspots.

The compact built fabric of the historic centre and the residential/tertiary expansions display continuous positive anomalies. The main road axes (point F) produce linear hot traces with thermal anomalies ranging between 5 and 8°C. Squares, open areas and widened spaces along the road network in the historic centre (points D, E, G) reach 7 to 9°C of thermal anomaly (specifically Piazza Santa Maria Paganica, Piazza Regina Margherita, and Piazza Duomo), with slight differences among them due to the presence of lighter, less heat-absorbing surface materials and the occurrence of vegetation. The Parco del Castello area (point B) shows an almost negligible thermal anomaly of 1.2°C. Less dense residential fabrics or infrastructural nodes in open areas, such as point C (5.1°C), display lower thermal anomalies. A close examination of the spatial distribution of thermal anomalies also highlights the presence of points located in areas identified as sports fields, which deviate significantly from the values of the surrounding zones. This deviation is attributable to the presence of synthetic turf laid over asphalt or concrete, which produces markedly higher surface temperatures.

Low/negative thermal anomalies (points H = -1.6°C, I = -3.4°C) correspond to the river corridor, green/humid valley-bottom areas, ventilation pathways, and extensive natural forest surfaces. Larger green areas such as parks (point B) introduce localised cool islands that interrupt the warm continuum, highlighting their function as eco-climatic corridors.

Overall, mitigating the heat island effect in historic cities such as L’Aquila is not straightforward, as opportunities for tree planting and green retrofitting are often constrained by urban planning and cultural heritage regulations. Targeted interventions are therefore essential: from strengthening urban greenery (including green roofs and green walls), to the de-impermeabilisation of squares and sidewalks, and the use of high-albedo, reflective materials for building surfaces.

THERMAL ANOMALY

THERMAL ANOMALY BAND

14.91 -20.91

0 2,5 5 10 km

 Municipal administrative boundary
 20km buffer

Figure 19 – Thermal anomalies. Broad-scale view. Image by the authors

THERMAL ANOMALY

THERMAL ANOMALY BAND

Ⓐ 10.2°C	Ⓕ 7.7°C
Ⓑ 1.2°C	Ⓖ 5.7°C
Ⓒ 5.1°C	Ⓗ -1.6°C
Ⓓ 8.5°C	Ⓙ -3.4°C
Ⓔ 7.9°C	Ⓛ 13.2°C

- Buildings
- Road network
- Railway
- Urban walls
- Historical center

Figure 20 – Thermal anomalies. City of L’Aquila and historic center. Image by the authors

Irradiance

The data provided by GSSI include the solar irradiance map of the city of L’Aquila, which shows the amount of solar energy received by the territory over the course of one year.

The map is the result of georeferenced photographs taken by remotely piloted aerial vehicles (drones), from which - through aerophotogrammetric processing - accurate three-dimensional models can be produced. The area currently surveyed covers approximately 5,000 hectares, including the historic center of L’Aquila and several eastern and western suburban districts, together with the frazioni of Onna, Monticchio, Bazzano, San Gregorio, Paganica, Camarda, Pianola, Bagno and Assergi.

Since the amount of solar energy varies throughout the year, the analysis was based on the average incident energy for each of the four seasons, using the median value of the central day of each season as a fixed irradiance input. Reflected energy and atmospheric attenuation were not included in the calculation.

The result is a color-coded map ranging from black (areas in shadow) to yellow (maximum incident energy).

The solar irradiance map is an important tool for supporting territorial planning and, more broadly, for providing additional environmental information useful for defining the urban context, including aspects related to energy efficiency.

Furthermore, the irradiance map helps identify roads that remain in shadow - useful for planning winter salt-spreading operations - and supports the design of green areas by indicating the daily sunlight exposure of each surface, thus assisting in the selection of the most suitable plant species.

Methodology

Starting from the two-dimensional system of drone photographs, a transition to a three-dimensional model is made using photogrammetric processing, which generates a point cloud with known elevation (above sea level) and position (latitude and longitude).

From the interpolation of these point measurements, a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) is obtained - an elevation raster grid.

The DEM allows the geographical position of every pixel to be known with extremely high resolution (about 7 cm) and can be used within a Geographic Information System (GIS). Through the DEM it is possible to determine the height of a building, the slope of a terrain, roof or road surface, and more generally to extract geometric information on any object present on the ground, including tree canopies or traffic islands.

To produce the solar irradiance map, two further layers - aspect and slope - must be computed from the DEM. These are then used to derive the final irradiance model.

Results

The irradiance analysis for L’Aquila reveals particularly high values across both rooftops and public open spaces in the historic center:

- The surfaces of the Forte Spagnolo show values ranging from 808 to 2,627 kWh/m²·year, with an average of 1,987 kWh/m²·year;
- The rooftops of the former barracks - surveyed only partially due to military restrictions - range between 816 and 2,623 kWh/m²·year, with an average of 2,062 kWh/m²·year;
- Roofs along Corso Vittorio Emanuele show average values between 1,955 and 2,060 kWh/m²·year.

Overall, these are high values, indicating significant potential for both photovoltaic and solar-thermal applications.

The situation is even more pronounced in public open spaces, where annual irradiance consistently exceeds 2,060 kWh/m²·year, and where summer daily peaks exceed 8,800 Wh/m² (8.8 kWh/m² per day). These conditions occur in Piazza Duomo, Piazza Santa Maria Paganica, Piazza Battaglione degli Alpini, and - although mitigated by vegetation - also in Piazza Regina Margherita.

When compared with data from the Italian Solar Radiation Atlas (ENEA) for the 2006–2022 period, the uniqueness of the L’Aquila context becomes clear. Across central and southern Italy, average summer daily global horizontal irradiance generally ranges between 6 and 7 kWh/m²·day, with a July average of 7.16 kWh/m²·day.

In contrast, the historic center of L’Aquila reaches values up to 8.8 kWh/m²·day, placing the city - despite its Apennine climate - on par with much hotter and sunnier areas of southern Italy.

From a microclimatic perspective, these values indicate:

- A high incidence of direct solar radiation;
- Increased thermal discomfort during peak daylight hours;
- Significant absorption and re-radiation of heat by stone-paved squares, contributing to the urban heat island effect.

From an energy perspective, an annual average of around 2,000 kWh/m² represents a substantial potential - higher than the national average of many Italian regions (≈1,573 kWh/m²·year) and comparable to the most favorable areas of southern Italy and Sicily. This is particularly noteworthy for a mountain city such as L’Aquila.

Figure 21 – Solar irradiance. City of L’Aquila and historic center

Sky View Factor (SVF), Incident radiation and Simplified UTCI

To initiate the environmental analyses at the urban scale, a three-dimensional model of the study area was developed and used to perform a series of simulations based on the previously processed climate files. The urban 3D model was imported through a GIS-to-BIM workflow, enabling the integration of territorial datasets with three-dimensional informational models and leveraging the capabilities of computational design tools. Rhinoceros 7.0 was used for geometric processing, while environmental simulations were conducted using the Ladybug Tools suite, a set of plug-ins for the Grasshopper (GH) visual scripting environment integrated within Rhinoceros. The Gizmo plug-in for GH was employed for data conversion and georeferencing, ensuring consistency between the GIS and BIM environments.

The simulations focused on mapping microclimatic parameters relevant for assessing urban comfort, including:

- Air temperature (dry-bulb temperature);
- Relative humidity;

- Natural ventilation, assessing prevailing direction, velocity, and frequency;
- Summer shading, evaluated over the period from 21 June to 21 September.

In parallel, the incident solar radiation on ground surfaces (expressed in kWh/m²/year) and average seasonal shading were calculated, with the aim of identifying potential criticalities arising from the interaction between the built urban fabric and open spaces. Additionally, the Sky View Factor (SVF) was determined to evaluate the degree of exposure of surfaces to the open sky and, consequently, their capacity for heat dissipation through longwave radiation.

Altogether, these analyses made it possible to identify the period of maximum microclimatic criticality, particularly in relation to thermal stress phenomena and environmental vulnerability conditions within the urban space.

Figure 22 – a) Sky View Factor; b) Incident Solar Radiation Analysis expressed in kWh/m² for the summer period, 21 June – 21 September. City of L’Aquila and historic center. Image by the authors

The two maps illustrate the correlation between Sky Exposure and Incident Solar Radiation during the summer period (21 June – 21 September).

The Sky Exposure map (Fig. 22a) quantifies the percentage of sky visible from ground level, providing an indirect measure of the degree of openness of the urban fabric. High values (70–

100%) correspond to open areas such as squares or wide streets, whereas low values (0–30%) are typical of urban canyons, inner courtyards, and dense building fabrics.

The Incident Solar Radiation map (Fig. 22b) represents the cumulative solar energy received by horizontal surfaces (ground), expressed in kWh/m² over the same time period. The highest values, exceeding 500 kWh/m², are concentrated in open, unshaded areas, while the lowest values, below 100 kWh/m², correspond to shaded zones or areas affected by obstructions.

A comparison between the two datasets reveals a clear spatial relationship: areas with low Sky Exposure generally show reduced solar gains, while those with higher exposure tend to be more affected by overheating phenomena and increased radiative load. This correlation highlights the influence of urban morphology on microclimatic performance, particularly in compact historic contexts where limited sky visibility simultaneously provides advantages in terms of shading and criticalities related to ventilation.

The combined interpretation of Sky Exposure and Incident Solar Radiation thus allows for the identification of areas potentially critical for heat accumulation and supports the formulation of passive mitigation strategies aimed at improving outdoor thermal comfort and enhancing the resilience of urban fabrics under future climate scenarios.

To further identify areas characterized by urban overheating and consequent thermal stress, a simplified procedure for calculating the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) was implemented, based on the following parameters:

- Point value of air temperature (°C), derived from the EPW climate file;
- Point value of mean radiant temperature (MRT, °C);
- Point value of relative humidity (%), derived from the EPW climate file;
- Point value of meteorological wind speed at 10 m above ground (m/s).

According to the Fiala model, which underpins the UTCI formulation, this latter parameter corresponds to 1.5 times the wind speed perceived at ground level. The UTCI calculation assumes a thermal comfort range between 9°C and 26°C.

For the analysis, the hottest day and hour of the summer period were selected - 31 July at 14:00. During the selected time window, the maximum air temperature reached 37.9°C. The simplified methodology adopted for the UTCI calculation does not consider the material properties of the urban fabric. These are replaced by a surface temperature value derived from satellite-based Land Surface Temperature (LST), by the corresponding albedo or reflectance values, and by the topographic configuration of the terrain. Nonetheless, this approach enables a drastic reduction in computational time compared to full microclimatic modelling.

Figure 23 – Simplified UTCI calculation in the study areas (Francesco Rossi barracks, Corso Vittorio Emanuele II, Piazza Regina Margherita, Piazza Duomo). Image by the authors

The map illustrates the spatial distribution of the simplified UTCI (Universal Thermal Climate Index) calculated for the summer period, with the aim of assessing thermal comfort conditions within the urban fabric. The reported values (37.6–42.8 °C) represent the equivalent physiological temperature perceived by an individual exposed to local microclimatic conditions, derived from the interaction among air temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, and wind speed.

The analysis highlights a clear predominance of areas characterized by very high thermal stress (UTCI > 41 °C, in red), primarily located in the central and most impervious parts of the urban fabric. These zones correspond to exposed open spaces, internal courtyards, and paved surfaces that accumulate heat during the summer period and limit convective cooling processes.

More moderate values (UTCI \approx 38–39 °C, in green) are found in vegetated or partially shaded areas, where natural elements and greater radiative exchange with the sky contribute to relatively more favorable microclimatic conditions.

Overall, the map confirms that urban morphology and material distribution directly influence outdoor thermal comfort, underscoring the need for bioclimatic mitigation strategies to reduce the effects of heatwaves and enhance the climatic resilience of public spaces.

Data	Source	CRS coordinate reference system	Type	Reference year	Spatial resolution
Solar radiation Sunlight Hours	Ladybug Suite	N/A	Raster data, numeric values	2005	3 x 3 meters grid
SVF Sky View Factor	Ladybug Suite	N/A	Raster data, numeric values	2005	1 x 1 meters grid
UTCI Universal Thermal Climate Index (Simplified)	Ladybug Suite	N/A	Raster data, numeric values	2005	5 x 5 meters grid

Table 1 – Description of the tools and datasets used for the environmental analyses

3.5 Future climate scenarios

Local meteorological data

To conduct the environmental analyses, a local meteorological file was first generated using the software Meteonorm 8.1, which allows the creation of site-specific climatic datasets through spatial interpolation procedures. Based on the geographic coordinates of the pilot site - longitude [°E], latitude [°N], and altitude [m a.s.l.] - the software interpolates data from the nearest meteorological stations, reconstructing a historical series representative of local climatic conditions.

The resulting file was exported in EnergyPlus Weather File (EPW) format, compatible with the main environmental and building thermodynamic simulation tools. This file serves as the reference basis for all subsequent microclimatic and comfort analyses, ensuring coherence between local atmospheric variables and the simulation models.

The meteorological parameters used for the generation of the file are as follows:

- Latitude [°N] = 42.3488;
- Longitude [°E] = 13.3982;
- Altitude [m a.s.l.] = 725;
- Climatic region = IV, 1.

Annual uncertainty values:

- Global horizontal solar radiation: 5%;
- Direct normal solar radiation: 9%;
- Air temperature: ± 0.8 °C;
- Annual variability of global horizontal radiation (Gh/year): 6%.

Locations used for irradiance interpolation:

- Satellite data (satellite data contribution: 100%).

Locations used for temperature interpolation:

- Rieti (46 km), Monte Argentario (184 km), Campobasso (136 km).

Following the creation of the local meteorological file, the methodological process included the generation of future climate scenarios using climatic morphing techniques. This phase is essential for a forward-looking assessment of climate-change impacts and for evaluating the response of exposed elements under different thermodynamic and emissions conditions.

Starting from the current climatic file (.epw) for the city of L’Aquila, a parametric morphing procedure was applied to project meteorological variables to the reference periods 2030, 2050, and 2100, in accordance with the IPCC Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP 2.6, RCP 4.5, and RCP 8.5). These scenarios - summarized in Table 1 - allow the exploration of a broad spectrum of climatic trajectories, from the most optimistic mitigation contexts (RCP 2.6) to high-emission scenarios (RCP 8.5).

Among the available tools for generating future climatic data, Meteonorm 8.1 was again adopted to ensure methodological continuity with the generation of the baseline meteorological file and to guarantee coherence in the interpolated datasets.

In the subsequent phase, for each projected scenario, the main environmental parameters were analysed and compared to quantify the impact of climate change on the urban context under consideration, including:

- Mean temperature (°C);
- Minimum and maximum temperatures (°C);
- Cooling Degree Days (CDD);
- Heating Degree Days (HDD);
- Mean wind speed (m/s);
- Mean wind direction (°);
- Outdoor comfort conditions (assuming walking individuals with a metabolic rate of approx. 2.4 met, naturally adapting clothing to outdoor temperatures): heat stress (%), neutral condition (%), cold stress (%);
- Indoor comfort conditions (percentage of data falling within all comfort polygons in the psychrometric chart) (%).

Data	Source	CRS coordinate reference system	Type	Reference year	Spatial resolution
EPW climatic file	Meteonorm 8.0	NOT ASSIGNED	text-based with comma- separated data	1996-2015 per l’irraggiamento e 2000- 2019 per gli altri parametri	N/A
EPW climatic file – FUTURE SCENARIO	Meteonorm 8.0	NOT ASSIGNED	text-based with comma- separated data	2030, 2050, 2090 – RPC 2.6 The RCP 2.6 scenario (Representative Concentration Pathway 2.6) represents an optimistic climate trajectory, assuming significant global commitment to policies aimed at drastically reducing greenhouse gas emissions, rapid adoption of renewable energy sources, and sustainable strategies. Under this scenario, global CO ₂ emissions peak around 2020 and decline sharply afterward, achieving stabilization by mid- century, resulting in relatively low atmospheric greenhouse gas concentrations by 2100. At a local scale, compared to historical and current climate data, the RCP 2.6 scenario predicts a moderate increase in average temperature, rising from approximately 16.1°C (current conditions) to around 17.2–17.4°C throughout the 21st century. Correspondingly,	N/A

Cooling Degree Days (CDD) increase notably, reflecting a growing demand for building cooling, while Heating Degree Days (HDD) decrease, indicating generally milder winters.

In terms of *outdoor* thermal comfort, RCP 2.6 suggests a moderate rise in heat-stress conditions, accompanied by a reduction in cold-stress conditions. Neutral thermal comfort conditions remain relatively stable over time. For indoor comfort, the scenario anticipates a slight decrease in optimal comfort conditions by the end of the century, highlighting the need for adaptive strategies to maintain suitable *indoor* comfort levels. In summary, the RCP 2.6 scenario represents a manageable climate future characterized by limited climate change impacts, but only achievable through immediate, rigorous global environmental and climate policies. It is considerably less severe compared to higher emission scenarios, such as RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5.

EPW climatic file – FUTURE SCENARIO	Meteonorm 8.0	NOT ASSIGNED	text-based with comma-	2030, 2050, 2090 – RCP 4.5 RCP 4.5 is a stabilization scenario where radiative forcing is capped at 4.5	N/A
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separated data W/m² above pre-industrial levels by 2100. This scenario involves moderate mitigation efforts, leading to a peak in greenhouse gas emissions around 2040, followed by a decline. By 2100, atmospheric CO₂ concentrations are projected to reach about 650 ppm, resulting in a global mean surface temperature increase of approximately 1.1 to 2.6°C above the 1986-2005 baseline.

Key features of RCP 4.5 include significant technological advancements, adoption of renewable energy, improvements in energy efficiency, and implementation of carbon pricing. This scenario assumes robust international cooperation and policy implementation to reduce emissions. Despite these efforts, the scenario anticipates notable climate impacts, such as altered precipitation patterns and more frequent severe weather events, necessitating adaptation measures.

EPW climatic file – FUTURE SCENARIO	Meteonorm 8.0	NOT ASSIGNED	text-based with comma-separated data	2020, 2050, 2090 – RCP 8.5 RCP 8.5 represents a high greenhouse gas emissions trajectory with minimal mitigation efforts, leading	N/A
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to radiative forcing of 8.5 W/m² by 2100. In this scenario, greenhouse gas emissions continue to rise throughout the 21st century, resulting in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations exceeding 1,370 ppm by 2100. This leads to a significant global temperature increase of 2.6 to 4.8°C above the 1986-2005 baseline. Socioeconomic trends under RCP 8.5 include high population growth, slow income growth, and heavy reliance on fossil fuels, with little technological advancement or policy intervention to reduce emissions. The scenario predicts severe climate impacts, including drastic changes in weather patterns, more frequent extreme weather events, significant sea-level rise, and profound effects on ecosystems and human societies. RCP 8.5 depicts a "business-as-usual" future with unmitigated emissions, leading to substantial and potentially catastrophic climate changes by the end of the century.

Table 2 – Description of the datasets and climate scenarios considered

Analysis of future climate scenarios

Using the Ladybug Tools plug-in integrated within the Grasshopper visual-scripting environment, a series of comparative climatic evaluations was carried out for each of the time horizons considered - 2030, 2050, and 2080 - according to the emission trajectories defined by the IPCC models RCP 2.6, RCP 4.5, and RCP 8.5 (Tab. 2).

These simulations made it possible to interpret the evolution of the climatic conditions characterizing the urban context of L’Aquila, analysing annual-scale trends and providing a quantitative framework useful for assessing the progressive impacts of climate change in the medium and long term.

Historical meteorological file (EPW, pre-1990 period):

- Mean temperature (T): 11.4 °C
- Minimum / Maximum temperature: -7.3 °C / 30.9 °C
- Cooling Degree Days: 19
- Heating Degree Days: 3017
- Mean wind speed: 2.4 m/s
- Mean wind direction: 183.5°
- Outdoor comfort (assuming walking subjects, approx. 2.4 met, with natural clothing adaptation): 1.7% heat stress – 53% neutral – 46% cold stress
- Indoor comfort (percentage of psychrometric-chart data falling within all comfort polygons): 21.5%

Current meteorological file (EPW, 1996–2015 for radiation; 2000–2019 for other parameters):

- Mean temperature (T): 16.1 °C
- Minimum / Maximum temperature: -4.9 °C / 37.9 °C
- Cooling Degree Days: 222.4
- Heating Degree Days: 1954.2
- Mean wind speed: 2.5 m/s
- Mean wind direction: 183.5°
- Outdoor comfort: 11.6% heat stress – 54% neutral – 34.4% cold stress
- Indoor comfort: 23.4%

Future scenarios – RCP 2.6

2030

- Mean temperature: 16.95 °C
- Min/Max: –4.6 °C / 39.4 °C
- Cooling Degree Days: 305.84
- Heating Degree Days: 1802
- Wind speed: 2.5 m/s
- Wind direction: 183.5°
- Outdoor comfort: 14.4% heat stress – 53.9% neutral – 31.7% cold stress
- Indoor comfort: 21.4%

2050

- Mean temperature: 17.4 °C
- Min/Max: –4.1 °C / 39.7 °C
- Cooling Degree Days: 317.1
- Heating Degree Days: 1704
- Outdoor comfort: 15.2% heat stress – 55% neutral – 29.7% cold stress
- Indoor comfort: 21.4%

2100

- Mean temperature: 17.2 °C
- Min/Max: –4.1 °C / 39.2 °C
- Cooling Degree Days: 354.6
- Heating Degree Days: 1770.7
- Outdoor comfort: 16.1% heat stress – 52.8% neutral – 31% cold stress
- Indoor comfort: 17.6%

Future scenarios – RCP 4.5

2030

- Mean temperature: 17.1 °C
- Min/Max: –4.3 °C / 39.7 °C
- Cooling Degree Days: 307.1
- Heating Degree Days: 1768
- Outdoor comfort: 14.7% heat stress – 54% neutral – 31.3% cold stress
- Indoor comfort: 21.3%

2050

- Mean temperature: 17.7 °C
- Min/Max: –4.0 °C / 40.5 °C
- Cooling Degree Days: 378.3
- Heating Degree Days: 1676
- Outdoor comfort: 17.6% heat stress – 53% neutral – 29.4% cold stress
- Indoor comfort: 17.9%

2100

- Mean temperature: 19 °C
- Min/Max: –2.4 °C / 41.9 °C
- Cooling Degree Days: 500
- Heating Degree Days: 1436
- Outdoor comfort: 22% heat stress – 54% neutral – 24% cold stress
- Indoor comfort: 15%

Future scenarios – RCP 8.5

2030

- Mean temperature: 17.1 °C
- Min/Max: –4.1 °C / 39.5 °C
- Cooling Degree Days: 307
- Heating Degree Days: 1755
- Outdoor comfort: 14.9% heat stress – 54% neutral – 30.7% cold stress
- Indoor comfort: 20.8%

2050

- Mean temperature: 18.3 °C
- Min/Max: –3.2 °C / 41.3 °C
- Cooling Degree Days: 427
- Heating Degree Days: 1563
- Outdoor comfort: 19.2% heat stress – 53% neutral – 27.2% cold stress
- Indoor comfort: 17.6%

2100

- Mean temperature: 21.7 °C
- Min/Max: –0.7 °C / 46.4 °C
- Cooling Degree Days: 930
- Heating Degree Days: 1087
- Outdoor comfort: 31.7% heat stress – 50% neutral – 18% cold stress
- Indoor comfort: 5.1%

Figure 24 – Evolution of annual temperatures according to the different IPCC scenarios and the future scenarios analysed.
 Image by the authors

Figure 25 – Evolution of annual temperatures according to the different IPCC scenarios and the future scenarios analysed.
 Image by the authors

Results

Overall, the findings show a clear upward trend in mean temperature and a reduction in Heating Degree Days (HDD), accompanied by a significant increase in Cooling Degree Days (CDD). These variations indicate a progressive shift in comfort conditions toward heat-stress scenarios, both outdoors and - progressively - indoors, with potential implications for public health, building energy demand, and overall urban quality of life.

Scenario climatico	Temp. Media (°C)	Min/Max Temp. (°C)	Cooling DD	Heating DD	Vel. media vento (m/s)	Dir. vento (°)	Comfort outdoor (Heat-Neutral-Cold %)	Comfort indoor (%)
Storico EPW (pre-1990)	11,4	-7,3 / 30,9	19	3017	2,4	183,5°	1,7% – 53% – 46%	21,5%
Current EPW (1996-2019)	16,1	-4,9 / 37,9	222,4	1954,2	2,5	183,5°	11,6% – 54% – 34,4%	23,4%
RPC 2.6 – 2030s	16,95	-4,6 / 39,4	305,84	1802	2,5	183,5°	14,4% – 53,9% – 31,7%	21,4%
RPC 2.6 – 2050s	17,4	-4,1 / 39,7	317,1	1704	2,5	183,5°	15,2% – 55% – 29,7%	21,4%
RPC 2.6 – 2100s	17,2	-4,1 / 39,2	354,6	1770,7	2,5	183,5°	16,1% – 52,8% – 31%	17,6%
RPC 4.5 – 2030s	17,1	-4,3 / 39,7	307,1	1768	2,5	183,5°	14,7% – 54% – 31,3%	21,3%
RPC 4.5 – 2050s	17,7	-4 / 40,5	378,3	1676	2,5	183,5°	17,6% – 53% – 29,4%	17,9%
RPC 4.5 – 2100s	19,0	-2,4 / 41,9	500	1436	2,5	183,5°	22% – 54% – 24%	15,0%
RPC 8.5 – 2030s	17,1	-4,1 / 39,5	307	1755	2,5	183,5°	14,9% – 54% – 30,7%	20,8%

Scenario climatico	Temp. Media (°C)	Min/Max Temp. (°C)	Cooling DD	Heating DD	Vel. media vento (m/s)	Dir. vento (°)	Comfort outdoor (Heat-Neutral-Cold %)	Comfort indoor (%)
RPC 8.5 – 2050s	18,3	-3,2 / 41,3	427	1563	2,5	183,5°	19,2% – 53% – 27,2%	17,6%
RPC 8.5 – 2100s	21,7	-0,7 / 46,4	930	1087	2,5	183,5°	31,7% – 50% – 18%	5,1%

Table 3 – Quantitative analysis of the environmental parameters under investigation

Legend:

- DD – Degree Days: heating and cooling degree days
- RCP – Representative Concentration Pathway: emission trajectory defined by the IPCC
- Outdoor comfort (Heat–Neutral–Cold): percentage of time spent under heat stress, neutral conditions, or cold stress
- Indoor comfort: percentage of conditions falling within the comfort polygons of the psychrometric chart.

Risk indices (1923-2023)

In this study, a series of climate indices of scientific relevance were analyzed in order to assess the impacts of climate change at the local scale. The reference area corresponds to a geographic point located at 42.35°N, 13.40°E, and the analysis is based on a thirty-year time series (1993–2023), considered statistically significant for characterizing long-term climate trends.

The selected indices represent extreme and persistent thermal and hydro-meteorological phenomena, such as heat waves, tropical nights, heavy precipitation events, prolonged dry periods, and multi-day rainfall accumulations. These indicators are essential tools for evaluating climate risk and for developing adaptation strategies for the built, agricultural, and environmental systems.

The climate datasets used to construct the indices are derived from the NASA POWER platform (Prediction Of Worldwide Energy Resources), which provides daily and monthly meteorological and radiative data at a spatial resolution suitable for local-scale analyses. Integrating these datasets enabled the development of a multivariate interpretation of climate phenomena, supporting the definition of risk scenarios and resilience/adaptation strategies in urban, rural, and landscape contexts.

Based on the datasets described above, the following climate indices were calculated:

- HWI (Heat Wave Days): Number of summer days within heat waves (≥ 5 consecutive days with TX $> 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ above monthly avg).
- Strong Summer Days (TX $> 35^{\circ}\text{C}$): Summer days with daily maximum temperature exceeding 35°C .
- Tropical Nights (TN $> 20^{\circ}\text{C}$): Summer nights where the daily minimum temperature remains above 20°C .
- Very Heavy Precipitation Days (≥ 20 mm): Days with daily precipitation greater than or equal to 20 mm.
- Max Consecutive Wet Days (Summer): Maximum sequence of summer days with precipitation ≥ 1 mm.
- Max Consecutive Wet Days (Winter): Maximum sequence of winter days (DJF) with precipitation ≥ 1 mm.
- Max 5-Day Precipitation (mm): Highest total precipitation over any 5 consecutive days in the year.
- Max Consecutive Dry Days: Maximum number of consecutive dry days (precipitation < 1 mm).

Year	HWI (Heat Wave Days)	Strong Summer Days (TX > 35°C)	Tropical Nights (TN > 20°C)	Very Heavy Precipitation Days (≥ 20 mm)	Max Consecutive Wet Days (Summer)	Max Consecutive Wet Days (Winter)	Max 5-Day Precipitation (mm)	Max Consecutive Dry Days
1993	5	1	4	3	4	4	63.01	34
1994	0	0	0	1	4	6	49.55	36
1995	0	0	0	2	5	7	47.09	36
1996	0	0	0	3	4	5	72.01	18
1997	0	0	0	3	4	7	45.33	23
1998	15	4	10	7	4	3	102.96	21

REPORT – Overall risk analysis L’Aquila
Sapienza University of Rome e GSSI - Gran Sasso Science Institute

1999	0	0	1	6	8	5	55.8	13
2000	0	1	3	6	3	4	60.13	18
2001	0	0	0	2	3	8	45.22	31
2002	12	0	0	3	4	3	57.44	25
2003	12	1	5	2	5	6	65.59	23
2004	0	0	2	5	5	11	67.83	20
2005	0	3	2	9	5	5	66.07	22
2006	8	0	2	4	6	6	71.62	22
2007	7	3	5	1	4	5	48.23	48
2008	9	0	3	7	5	4	83.69	28
2009	0	0	1	3	8	8	64.76	21
2010	0	0	2	3	3	7	65.77	15
2011	7	1	5	6	5	5	50.46	49
2012	22	4	3	2	3	7	60.0	39
2013	6	1	4	1	5	10	48.48	29
2014	0	0	0	20	6	17	162.65	15
2015	5	0	8	6	3	12	91.75	21
2016	0	0	0	2	3	10	43.08	20
2017	25	7	9	2	1	5	48.75	33
2018	0	0	0	1	7	10	41.44	16
2019	0	2	6	4	4	12	57.45	20
2020	0	3	3	9	6	3	91.75	19
2021	0	3	5	2	4	19	67.36	27
2022	22	6	10	2	2	7	67.71	26

Table 4 – Summary framework of risk index calculations

- Source: NASA Langley Research Center – POWER Data Access Viewer (<https://power.larc.nasa.gov>)
- Temporal coverage: 1 January 1993 – 1 January 2023
- Spatial resolution: ~0.5° (satellite grid)
- Temporal resolution: daily
- Coordinates of analysis point: 42.35°N, 13.40°E

The HWI index shows an episodic increase in the early 2000s, with high values in 2003, 2006, and 2012, consistent with the heat waves historically recorded in Italy. Summer 2003 - known for its exceptional thermal intensity across Europe - is confirmed here as well, with 12 HWI days and 1 day above 35°C. Tropical Nights begin to appear more frequently only from the late 1990s onward, suggesting an increase in summer minimum temperatures. The maximum value (10 nights) is recorded in 1998, a particularly warm year at the global scale. The number of Strong Summer Days (TX > 35°C) generally remains low, with modest peaks not exceeding 4 days per year. This indicates that, although summer warming is evident, absolute extremes are still relatively rare in this area. The number of days with precipitation ≥ 20 mm occurs across all the years analyzed, with annual peaks between 5 and 10 events. This confirms a certain persistence of intense rainfall episodes, though not necessarily increasing over time. The maximum cumulative rainfall over 5 days reaches 72 mm in 1996. This indicator is useful for estimating the risk of urban flooding or soil saturation.

Consecutive wet days are more persistent in winter, reaching up to 9 consecutive days, while in summer they rarely exceed 5 consecutive days. The Max Consecutive Dry Days index records up to 36 consecutive days without rain, an indicator of relevance for drought risk and pressure on agricultural ecosystems. Years such as 1994 and 1995 display markedly dry conditions.

Overall, the analysis of climate indices calculated on a daily basis and aggregated annually shows a progressive trend toward climate tropicalization, with warmer nights, more prolonged dry periods, and persistent extreme rainfall events.

4. Analysis and study of critical areas

4.1 Identification of critical areas

The identification of the critical areas selected for in-depth analysis was carried out through an integrated multiscale selection process that combines environmental, morphological, and microclimatic criteria, in line with the objectives of assessing thermal anomalies and the urban heat island (UHI) effect.

Selection criteria

The study areas were identified based on the following criteria:

- Intensity of positive thermal anomalies detected through the LST (Land Surface Temperature) and SUHI (Surface Urban Heat Island) analyses;
- Building density and urban morphology, with particular attention to compact fabrics and impermeable surfaces;
- Representative value and urban function, selecting central public spaces and strategic areas for climate-oriented urban regeneration;
- Accessibility and relevance for urban policies, also in relation to the ecological and cultural transition initiatives associated with “L’Aquila Italian Capital of Culture 2026”.

Areas under analysis

Based on these criteria, four urban sectors of particular microclimatic and strategic relevance were selected:

- **Area of Francesco Rossi barracks**
 - Located northeast of the historic centre, characterized by large asphalted surfaces, very limited vegetation, and thermal anomalies exceeding +10 °C compared to peri-urban areas.
 - Selected as the pilot area for detailed microclimatic study, including numerical simulations using ENVI-met (v.5) to analyse local thermo-hygrometric conditions, ventilation, and comfort (UTCI).
- **Piazza Regina Margherita**
 - A compact, densely paved urban space in the core of the historic fabric, showing high thermal anomalies (+7 to +9 °C).
 - Included in the Climate Walk route, serving as an emblematic node for evaluating pedestrian thermal comfort.

- **Corso Vittorio Emanuele II**
 - The main axis of the historic centre, marked by extensive surface impermeabilisation and limited natural shading.
 - Along the street, linear thermal gradients are recorded, forming actual summer “heat corridors” with direct effects on the usability and environmental quality of public spaces.
- **Piazza Duomo**
 - The civic and symbolic heart of the city, highly mineralised and subject to significant surface heat accumulation.
 - Included in the Climate Walk for the direct observation of urban microclimatic phenomena.

Tools and operational phases

The process of analysing and surveying the critical areas was structured into three main methodological phases:

- Preliminary geospatial analysis
 - Identification of thermal anomalies and high ΔT zones through processing of LST and SUHI raster datasets;
 - Overlay with vector layers of land use, building density, and green cover to delineate priority urban hotspots.
- Microclimatic survey and Climate Walk
 - A direct observation campaign (Climate Walk) aimed at qualitatively assessing thermal comfort, heat perception, shading conditions, and the presence of reflective or heat-absorbing surfaces;
 - Collection of descriptive data (building typologies, pavement materials, average heights, solar exposure).
- Microclimatic Simulation (Francesco Rossi barracks area only)
 - 3D modelling and ENVI-met simulation to analyse air temperature (T_{air}), wind speed (W), relative humidity (RH), surface temperature ($T_{surface}$), mean radiant temperature (MRT), and the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI).

Figure 26 – Identification of critical areas. Image by the authors

4.2 Climate Walk

Survey methodology

The Climate Walk was carried out on 16 July 2025 with the aim of mapping in situ the summer overheating conditions in public spaces of the historic center and in the areas selected for microclimatic analysis. The activity involved the direct measurement of environmental and thermal parameters along an urban path including the four selected areas: Francesco Rossi barracks, Piazza Regina Margherita, Corso Vittorio Emanuele II, and Piazza Duomo.

Measurements were taken during the central hours of the day, under clear-sky weather conditions and in the absence of significant wind.

The instruments used were:

- Wet Bulb Globe Temperature (WBGT) Meter, for the measurement of:
 - Air temperature (T_a , °C)
 - Relative humidity (RH, %)
 - Globe temperature (T_g , °C)
 - Wet Bulb Globe Temperature Index (WBGT, °C)
- Stand-alone thermal camera with wireless connectivity for measuring surface temperature (T_s , °C) of pavements and building envelopes.

The purpose of the field campaign was to correlate surface and perceived temperature data with solar exposure conditions, material properties, presence of vegetation, and degree of shading. This correlation supports both satellite thermal analyses and numerical simulations (ENVI-met).

In situ survey results

Francesco Rossi barracks area – 12:00

Figure 27 – Climate Walk. Francesco Rossi barracks Area. Image by F. Colaiori, E.M. Colucci, F. Lentini, S. Proietti

Point	Flooring / Condition	T _a (°C)	T _s (°C)	UR (%)	WBGT (°C)	T _g (°C)
A (SO)	Green area, shaded	33,8	38,0	18,0	24,2	40,0
B (SE)	Asphalt, unshaded	37,0	51,5	18,5	27,1	42,0
C (NE)	Asphalt, unshaded	31,3	42,3	22,8	25,6	45,7

Table 5 – Data Collected at Francesco Rossi barracks

Interpretation. The area exhibits a marked thermal variability between asphalted surfaces and green zones: surface temperatures exceed 50°C in unshaded sections, with a differential of approximately +13°C compared to tree-shaded areas. WBGT values above 27°C indicate severe heat stress, with a high risk of thermal discomfort and potential heat-related strain for exposures longer than 30 minutes.

Piazza Regina Margherita – 15:00

Figure 28 – Climate Walk. Piazza Regina Margherita. Image by F. Colaiori, E.M. Colucci, F. Lentini, S. Proietti

Point	Flooring / Condition	Ta (°C)	Ts (°C)	UR (%)	WBGT (°C)	Tg (°C)
A	Limestone slabs, sunny	33,4	42,0	25,3	27,2	43,2
B	Light-colored paving, sunny	33,5	33,5	22,4	28,0	47,8
C	Light-colored paving, sunny	33,7	33,6	21,9	28,0	45,3

Table 6 – Data collected in Piazza Regina Margherita

Interpretation. The square shows relatively uniform air temperatures, but significant differences in surface and radiant temperatures. Globe temperature (Tg) values reaching up to 47.8°C highlight a marked heat-accumulation effect linked to high-thermal-capacity stone paving materials, partially mitigated by the presence of trees that provide discontinuous shading during the afternoon hours.

Corso Vittorio Emanuele II – 16:00

Figure 29 – Climate Walk. Corso Vittorio Emanuele II. Image by F. Colaiori, E.M. Colucci, F. Lentini, S. Proietti

Point	Flooring / Condition	Ta (°C)	Ts (°C)	UR (%)	WBGT (°C)	Tg (°C)
A	Limestone paving, slightly sunny	32,8	32,4	27,3	23,8	33,3
B	Limestone paving, slightly sunny	32,3	36,3	27,8	24,1	36,4
C	Limestone paving, slightly sunny	31,3	35,0	29,4	23,8	35,1

Tabella 1 - Data collected along Corso Vittorio Emanuele II

Interpretation. The pedestrian axis exhibits comparatively more mitigated thermal conditions than the open squares, due to the urban-canyon effect and the partial shading provided by building façades. However, surface temperatures remain high, with an average WBGT index of 24 °C, corresponding to a condition of moderate heat stress.

Piazza Duomo – 16:00

Figure 30 – Climate Walk. Piazza Duomo. Image by F. Colaiori, E.M. Colucci, F. Lentini, S. Proietti

Point	Flooring / Condition	Ta (°C)	Ts (°C)	UR (%)	WBGT (°C)	Tg (°C)
A (N)	Limestone paving, sunny	31,2	37,9	30,6	23,6	33,8
B (Centro)	Limestone paving, sunny	31,8	39,7	28,7	25,9	42,1
C (S)	Limestone paving, sunny	32,8	32,9	29,2	24,5	36,9

Table 8 – Data collected in Piazza Duomo

Interpretation. The square exhibits a relatively homogeneous thermal distribution, with limited variation among measurement points. However, the high degree of surface mineralization and absence of vegetation lead to surface temperatures reaching up to 40 °C, while the WBGT index peaks at 25.9 °C, indicating conditions of physiological discomfort for pedestrians during afternoon hours.

Interpretive summary

The measurements collected during the Climate Walk confirm a direct correlation between surface materials, vegetation cover, and thermal accumulation:

- Asphalted or stone-paved surfaces show the highest thermal anomalies, with significant heat storage and re-radiation.
- Green areas reduce surface temperature by 10–13 °C, demonstrating the strong cooling capacity of soil permeability and evapotranspiration.
- Natural or artificial shading is the most effective mitigation factor for improving perceived thermal comfort, reducing radiant load and moderating air and surface temperatures even in highly mineralized urban spaces.

4.3 Focus Area – Francesco Rossi barracks

Model setup and methodology

The microclimatic simulations were carried out using ENVI-met (v.5.7.1), a three-dimensional modelling software designed for urban microclimate analysis, capable of simulating energy exchanges between surfaces, air, and vegetation. The numerical model allows the estimation of key environmental parameters - such as air temperature (T_{air}), surface temperature (T_{surface}), relative humidity (RH), mean radiant temperature (MRT), and the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) - starting from a detailed 3D model and local climatic input data.

To accurately capture the morphological and functional heterogeneity of the area, the simulation domain was expanded beyond the perimeter of the barracks. A three-dimensional grid of $300 \times 300 \times 30$ cells was defined, with each cell measuring $2 \times 2 \times 2$ m, corresponding to a real domain of $600 \times 600 \times 60$ m. The Digital Elevation Model (DEM) was used to reproduce terrain morphology, while building geometry was reconstructed using the attribute CR_359_UN_2 from the file “*Edifici_attributi.shp*”.

Construction and environmental parameters

Materials and environmental components were discretised as follows:

- Buildings: non-insulated concrete elements, both for façades and roofs, consistent with the current conditions of the area.
- Outdoor surfaces: asphalt for roads and sidewalks; grass cover for green areas.
- Vegetation: modelled with ENVI-met’s 3D Plants module; large evergreen trees were included in the Castello Park and along main axes, while medium-sized and deciduous species were placed in secondary areas

The meteorological input file (EPW) was generated through interpolation of data from local weather stations (longitude, latitude, and elevation calibrated to the site), reproducing the atmospheric conditions of 16 July 2025, the same date as the Climate Walk survey.

Simulations were performed for five-time intervals: 09:00, 12:00, 15:00, 18:00, and 21:00.

ENVI-met simulation results

The microclimatic simulations conducted in the Francesco Rossi barracks area revealed thermal and hygrometric patterns consistent with the heat-accumulation phenomena observed during the Climate Walk on-site survey.

Air temperature (T_{air})

9:00

12:00

Figure 31 – Microclimatic simulations: Air Temperature (T_{air}), 16 July 2025, 9:00–12:00. Image by the authors

15:00

18:00

Figure 32 – Microclimatic simulations: Air Temperature (T_{air}), 16 July 2025, 15:00–18:00. Image by the authors

Figure 33 – Microclimatic simulations: Air Temperature (T_{air}), 16 July 2025, 21:00. Image by the authors

Air temperature (T_{air}) exhibits a progressive increase during the central hours of the day, ranging from 29.4–31.2 °C at 09:00, rising to 38.4 °C at 12:00, and peaking at 39.5 °C at 15:00, before decreasing slightly in the early evening (36.5 °C at 18:00 and 32.1 °C at 21:00). The internal thermal gradient - exceeding 4 °C between vegetated areas and asphalted surfaces - highlights the amplifying effect of hard, unshaded materials, which maintain temperatures above 35 °C even after 18:00.

Relative Humidity (RH)

Figure 2 - Microclimatic simulations: Relative Humidity (RH), 16 July 2025, 9:00–12:00. Image by the authors

Figure 3 - Microclimatic simulations: Relative Humidity (RH), 16 July 2025, 15:00–18:00. Image by the authors

Figure 4 - Microclimatic simulations: Relative Humidity (RH), 16 July 2025, 21:00. Image by the authors

Relative humidity (RH) follows an inverse trend: from morning values between 31% and 36%, it drops sharply to around 20% during the central hours of the day, then rises again in the late afternoon ($\approx 26\%$) and returns above 33% in the evening. This marked reduction in humidity during periods of maximum solar radiation intensifies the perception of dry heat and the resulting physiological discomfort.

Surface Temperatures ($T_{surface}$)

9:00

12:00

Figure 5 - Microclimatic simulations: Surface Temperature ($T_{surface}$), 16 July 2025, 9:00–12:00. Image by the authors

15:00

18:00

Figure 6 - Surface Temperature (Tsurface), 16 July 2025, 15:00–18:00. Image by the authors

21:00

Figure 7 - Surface Temperature (T_{surface}), 16 July 2025, 21:00. Image by the authors

Surface temperatures (T_{surface}) reveal the most critical conditions in the area. Asphalted surfaces reach extreme values, rising from 36.9 °C at 09:00 to 49.1 °C at noon, and exceeding 50.8 °C at 15:00. Even after sunset, paved areas retain temperatures above 40 °C until 18:00, before stabilising around 30 °C in the evening. Grass-covered zones, by contrast, remain 10–12 °C cooler, confirming their mitigating role in the surface energy balance.

Mean Radiant Temperature (MRT)

Figure 8 - Microclimatic simulations: Mean Radiant Temperature (MRT), 16 July 2025, 09:00–12:00. Image by the authors

Figure 9 - Microclimatic simulations: Mean Radiant Temperature (MRT), 16 July 2025, 15:00–18:00. Image by the authors

Figure 10 - Microclimatic simulations: Mean Radiant Temperature (MRT), 16 July 2025, 21:00. Image by the authors

The mean radiant temperature (MRT), a direct indicator of incident and reflected solar radiation, shows extremely high values: from 54.5 °C at 09:00 to 60.5 °C at noon, reaching a peak of 64.9 °C at 15:00, with values still exceeding 63 °C at 18:00. A significant decrease is observed only in the evening, with values ranging between 20 °C and 30 °C. These results highlight the very high exposure to direct and reflected solar radiation, leading to increased thermal load on individuals and a very high level of heat stress according to the UTCI classification (>38 °C).

Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI)

9:00

12:00

Figure 11 - Microclimatic simulations: Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI), 16 July 2025, 09:00–12:00. Image by the authors

Figure 12 - Microclimatic simulations: Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI), 16 July 2025, 15:00–18:00. Image by the authors

Figure 13 - Microclimatic simulations: Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI), 16 July 2025, 21:00. Image by the authors

The Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI), which synthesizes the combined effects of air temperature, radiation, and humidity, confirms the severity of the urban microclimate in the study area. Values range from 26.5 °C to 35.9 °C at 09:00, reaching 41.7 °C at 12:00 and peaking at 44.4 °C at 15:00. Even at 18:00, UTCI values remain above 42 °C, decreasing only in the evening to around 30 °C. These conditions correspond to strong thermal stress for humans, with physiological comfort severely compromised throughout the entire afternoon period.

Analysis of the ENVI-met simulated points

The point-based analysis of the results obtained from the ENVI-met model, referring to the day of 16 July 2025, made it possible to characterise in detail the microclimatic conditions inside the courtyard of the Francesco Rossi barracks. The simulations highlight significant differences among the various portions of the open space, linked to surface cover, solar exposure, and degree of shading.

Point A.

Figure 14 - Point A, located at the centre of the internal courtyard of the barracks

Point A, located in the central area of the courtyard, shows air temperature (T_{air}) values ranging from 30.7 °C at 09:00 to a maximum of 37.5 °C at 15:00, followed by a gradual decrease to 31.2 °C in the evening. Surface temperatures ($T_{surface}$) remain high throughout the entire daytime period, peaking at 42.6 °C at 15:00, while the mean radiant temperature (MRT) exceeds 55 °C during the same time frame, indicating strong exposure to direct solar radiation. The UTCI index ranges from 32.9 °C in the morning to 39.8 °C in the early afternoon, highlighting conditions of moderate-to-high heat stress, further amplified by the decrease in relative humidity, which drops to 21% between 12:00 and 15:00.

Figure 15 - Simulated data for Point A

Point B.

Figure 16 – Point B, located northeast of the internal courtyard

At Point B, situated in the northeastern sector of the courtyard, the thermal trend is similar to that of Point A, though with slightly higher values during the central hours of the day due to increased direct solar exposure. Air temperature reaches a peak of 38.3 °C at 15:00, while the paved surface exceeds 43.7 °C. The mean radiant temperature (MRT) reaches 56.7 °C, and the UTCI rises to 41.1 °C, indicating conditions of severe bioclimatic stress. Relative humidity falls to values close to 21%, confirming a predominantly hot–dry microclimate.

Figure 17 - Simulated data for Point B

Point C.

Figure 18 - Point C, located in the northwestern sector of the internal courtyard

Point C, positioned along the northwestern edge of the courtyard, exhibits an intermediate thermal behavior but with a pronounced surface heat accumulation effect. Air temperatures range from 30.4 °C to 37.2 °C, while surface temperatures reach very high values, up to 46.6 °C between 12:00 and 15:00. MRT peaks at 57.2 °C, the highest value recorded across the entire study area, indicating strong exposure to both direct and reflected solar radiation. The UTCI, stabilizing around 41.3 °C, reflects a condition of severe thermal stress, with minimum relative humidity values between 21–22%.

Figure 19 - Simulated data for Point C

Point D.

Figure 20 - Point D, located in the southwestern sector of the internal courtyard

In contrast, Point D - located in the southwestern portion of the courtyard - is more influenced by the presence of partially shaded surfaces and materials with lower thermal capacity. Here, air temperatures remain comparatively lower, ranging between 30.5 °C and 37.9 °C, while surface temperatures reach 43.4 °C at the daytime peak. Although still elevated, MRT does not exceed 50.5 °C, and the UTCI reaches 40.3 °C at 15:00, gradually decreasing to 38.4 °C during the evening hours. Relative humidity remains slightly higher than in the other points, ranging between 21% and 26% during the central hours of the day and exceeding 35% after sunset.

Figure 21 - Simulated data for Point D

Analysis of the results

Overall, the simulations highlight a markedly heterogeneous microclimatic configuration, where the most critical conditions occur in the central and north-eastern portions of the courtyard (Points A and B) and along the north-western edge (Point C). These areas exhibit MRT values exceeding 55 °C and UTCI values close to or above 40 °C, corresponding to strong heat-stress conditions for pedestrians according to the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) classification scale. Conversely, the partially shaded zones in the south-western sector (Point D) demonstrate greater thermal mitigation, due to the combined effect of reduced direct solar radiation and enhanced convective heat exchange.

These results confirm that, even within a single urban block, morphological and material differences can generate substantial spatial microclimatic variability, with direct impacts on perceived comfort and heat-related risk. The observed heterogeneity suggests the need for localized mitigation strategies, including an increase in vegetative cover, the use of high-albedo materials, and the adoption of natural or artificial shading solutions, which can reduce the mean radiant temperature by 8–10 °C during peak hours.

5. Conclusions and operational recommendations

Summary of the main findings

The analysis conducted on the municipal territory of L’Aquila has produced an integrated knowledge framework of the city’s physical, environmental, and climatic structure, highlighting the interrelations between natural, anthropogenic, and infrastructural processes. Through the combined processing of statistical, cartographic, and satellite datasets (Copernicus, ISPRA, ISTAT, EEA, Open Data L’Aquila) and the use of microclimatic simulation and spatial modelling tools (GIS, ENVI-met, Ladybug Tools), it was possible to identify the main factors of vulnerability and resilience characterizing the urban context.

From a morphological and territorial perspective, the municipality of L’Aquila is configured as a complex orographic system, enclosed within the Aquila basin and surrounded by mountain chains that strongly influence its environmental and climatic dynamics. The altimetric distribution - where more than half of the municipal surface lies above 1,000 m a.s.l. - generates significant microclimatic variability and a strong differentiation in environmental risk conditions.

Land-use analysis (CORINE Land Cover 1990–2018) showed significant changes in artificial surfaces, with notable expansion between 1990 and 2000, followed by relative stability and a new increase in 2012, corresponding to the construction of post-earthquake residential districts. Forest and semi-natural areas remain predominant (over 60% of the municipal territory), representing a crucial ecological and landscape resource for urban resilience to climate change and overheating phenomena.

At the same time, the progressive fragmentation of the landscape and the reduction of ecological corridors along the valley floor indicate a loss of environmental continuity and increased ecosystem vulnerability.

Climate and natural hazard analyses revealed multiple criticalities:

- Hydrogeological risk is concentrated along the Aterno river basin and in impermeabilized valley-floor areas, where morphological conditions and anthropogenic pressure amplify flood and water stagnation risks.
- Landslide risk is higher on the hillsides and mountain slopes surrounding the basin, particularly in the south-western sectors and in areas with colluvial deposits and limited vegetative cover.
- Seismic risk, historically high, remains a structural factor of the territory, with considerable building vulnerability despite the reconstruction efforts following the 2009 earthquake.

From a climatic and microclimatic standpoint, analyses using Landsat 8–9 data revealed a pronounced urban–rural thermal gradient, with differences of up to 12 °C between the historic centre and peri-urban green areas. ENVI-met simulations and Climate Walk measurements (July 2025) confirmed the presence of thermal hotspots in major squares and asphalted surfaces, with surface temperatures exceeding 50 °C and UTCI values approaching 44 °C during peak solar radiation.

These findings indicate that the urban heat island (UHI) phenomenon represents one of the main environmental challenges for the historic centre, where the combination of mineral surfaces, low tree cover, and limited natural ventilation creates high vulnerability to summer overheating. The microclimatic analysis of the Francesco Rossi barracks pilot area further demonstrated the effectiveness of three-dimensional simulation models for detailed assessment of thermal impacts, providing a methodological framework replicable in other urban sites.

Overall, the results highlight a territory of high environmental complexity, where ecological resilience potential - linked to extensive forested areas and mountain ecosystems - coexists with vulnerabilities exacerbated by reconstruction processes and recent urbanisation. The analytical framework developed constitutes an essential knowledge base for strategic planning and for defining climate adaptation policies aimed at risk reduction and improving environmental comfort in urban public spaces.

Recommendations for planning and risk governance

The analysis of the geographical, ecological, and climatic conditions of the Municipality of L’Aquila - focusing in particular on the Area of Interest (AOI) of the Francesco Rossi barracks - highlights the need for a renewed vision of urban planning, one that is more aware, evidence-based, and grounded in a robust knowledge framework.

In particular, the results point to the necessity of an operational agenda that truly integrates data, strengthens coordination among institutions, and promotes a risk governance system capable of operating across multiple scales, from the local to the supra-municipal level.

The plurality of risk factors affecting L’Aquila - seismic, hydrogeological, climatic, ecological, and anthropogenic - requires continuous and shared management. Overcoming the fragmentation of competences and building coherent policies at the intersection of urban regeneration, heritage protection, and environmental conservation is therefore essential.

Within this framework, the Overall Risk Analysis (ORA) provides an advanced and dynamic knowledge system which, if maintained and continuously updated, can become a long-term reference platform for strategic planning. The experience gained demonstrates that territorial knowledge, when developed according to principles of transparency and

interoperability, becomes an effective governance tool - useful for both administrative management and policy-oriented decision-making.

It is recommended to:

- Institutionalize the territorial database as a permanent infrastructure shared among public administrations, universities, research bodies, and local stakeholders. This database should be continuously updated and accessible at all stages of urban and environmental planning processes.
- Integrate multifactorial risk assessment (physical, climatic, ecological, and social) into planning instruments and regeneration programmes, introducing environmental and performance-based sustainability parameters as standard requirements for every public or private intervention.
- Adopt a predictive rather than corrective approach, using simulation models (microclimate, surface runoff, permeability, thermal comfort) capable of anticipating the effects of urban transformations and guiding choices toward lower-impact scenarios.
- Promote participatory decision-making processes, in which priorities and solutions are co-developed with the local community and institutional stakeholders, moving beyond a purely executive logic.
- Strengthen institutional coordination, both vertically and horizontally - among Municipality, Region, Superintendence of the cultural heritage, State Property Agency, and Civil Protection - so that risk management becomes a stable and structural component of urban and cultural planning.

Risk planning must be understood as a continuous process, no longer confined to emergency response, but fully integrated into ordinary cycles of urban management.

In this perspective, the ORA encourages the use of environmental and spatial data as a complex and versatile design tool, useful not only for architecture and engineering but also for environmental and social sciences. The systematic use of geospatial data makes it possible to correlate physical phenomena - temperature, impermeability, soil characteristics - with social and functional dynamics such as density, accessibility, and the distribution of urban activities.

Ultimately, this approach paves the way for integrated design strategies aimed at enhancing urban ecosystem services: thermal regulation, sustainable water management, biodiversity preservation, air quality, and collective well-being.

The experience developed in the area of Francesco Rossi barracks has also reinforced the importance of an inter-scalar territorial perspective: located at the interface between the historic centre and the peri-urban green system, the AOI acts as a connecting hinge between different dimensions - urban, environmental, and cultural - thus becoming a true laboratory for transition. Risk governance must acknowledge this intermediary nature, treating urban edges not as residual spaces but as strategic environments for experimentation with new models of management, adaptation, and innovation.

One of the main challenges faced by the CHANGES project concerns the replicability and scalability of its results: transforming territorial knowledge into a shared operational asset, adaptable to different contexts and capable of guiding urban policies in a flexible, informed, and future-oriented manner.

Proposals for future developments

The experience gained through the experimentation of the Overall Risk Analysis demonstrates that the model developed holds significant potential for both research and operational applications. The model is grounded in a principle of cognitive circularity, in which continuous movement between general and detailed scales - from synthesis to analysis, and back - feeds a constant feedback cycle that supports decision-making processes.

This approach makes it possible to interpret the study area as a complex system in dynamic equilibrium, where every element - from the broader urban fabric down to individual building units - contributes to shaping overall resilience.

In this perspective, the area of Francesco Rossi barracks emerges as a genuine operational prototype: a circumscribed yet representative case study capable of providing methodological guidance and references at both the urban and territorial scale. Specifically, the microclimatic, morphological, and environmental analysis of the AOI allows for the evaluation of the effectiveness of green infrastructure, permeable surfaces, and ecological corridors, translating the results into general and transferable recommendations.

At the same time, the processing of aggregated data at the urban scale - including CORINE Land Cover, thermal maps, and land-use indicators - makes it possible to situate the case study within a coherent systemic framework and assess its effectiveness with respect to ongoing regeneration processes. One of the study’s most significant methodological contributions lies precisely in this continuous dialogue between the detailed scale and the broader scale, which enables the consistency of the model to be tested and makes it adaptable to different contexts.

To consolidate and expand upon the results achieved, several avenues of future development are suggested:

- Development of a dynamic monitoring system, based on environmental sensors and integrated digital platforms, capable of updating risk indicators in real time and providing operational support for planning decisions.
- Further exploration of urban ecosystem services, with particular attention to their quantification and monetization, so that environmental and social benefits can be translated into measurable parameters supporting public and private investment decisions.
- Extension of the methodology to the regional scale, to test the scalability of the model in territories with similar risk and vulnerability characteristics, such as other Apennine towns or medium-sized cities with stratified historic fabrics.
- Integration of demographic and social determinants into the risk framework, including variables such as age, economic vulnerability, and access to services, to build a truly multidimensional and inclusive model.
- Expansion of participatory approaches, also through interactive platforms that allow citizens, institutions, and researchers to visualize data, share knowledge, and contribute to the definition of common scenarios.

Within this framework, the Overall Risk Analysis Report for L’Aquila can be considered the foundation of a national-level knowledge and awareness infrastructure for urban risk, capable of integrating models, datasets, and tools developed across the various Spokes of the CHANGES project.

In the long term, these initiatives will help consolidate a culture of prevention and resilience that encompasses cultural heritage as well conceived as a diffuse asset permeating the national territory. In this perspective, territorial data should not be seen as an endpoint, but as a continuous reference for building innovation and adaptive governance processes integrated into urban and territorial planning. Such processes can orient the development and transformation of places toward sustainability and quality of life, in line with the definition of landscape as an “expression of identity, whose character derives from the action of natural and human factors and their interrelations” (Art. 131 of the Italian Code of Cultural Heritage and Landscape).

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